

Outsourcing Responsibility:

*Non-Refoulement, Due Process, and the Human Consequences of
EU–Tunisia Border Cooperation*

**MA Thesis European Studies
European Policy Track**

by

Kristina Stolbova

UNIVERSITY
OF AMSTERDAM

Graduate School for Humanities

2025

Student number: 15668371

Supervisor: Dr. Maciej Krogel

Second reader: Dr. Matteo Fermeglia

Word count: 18,911

ABSTRACT

In this thesis I examine how EU-funded coastal surveillance in Tunisia affects the rights and well-being of migrants intercepted before reaching Europe. While these measures are presented as part of humanitarian and border-management efforts, they raise concerns about compliance with legal obligations under the 1951 Refugee Convention and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. I argue that the deployment of patrol vessels, radar systems, and border control training, funded through the EU's externalization agreements, has led to practices that compromise key protections such as non-refoulement and access to asylum procedures. Drawing on legal documents, NGO reports, academic research, and twelve interviews with legal and humanitarian professionals, I analyse how these agreements function in practice and what their concrete consequences are for migrants in Tunisia. My findings suggest that intercepted migrants often face indefinite detention, a lack of legal clarity, and limited access to medical or psychological support. The thesis combines legal analysis with a sociological perspective to offer a critical view on how the EU's externalized asylum system impacts those it claims to protect.

Keywords: EU externalization; Tunisia; asylum; non-refoulement; migrants; fundamental rights

Table of Contents

INTRODUCTION.....	3
Topic and Research Question.....	3
Literature Review.....	7
Methodology.....	12
CHAPTER 1: STRUCTURES OF EXTERNALIZATION.....	15
1.1 Evolution of EU-Tunisia Migration Cooperation.....	16
1.2 Legal Frameworks and Financial Channels.....	28
1.3 Institutional Responsibilities and Implementation Practices.....	35
CHAPTER 2: LAW WITHOUT PROTECTION?.....	39
2.1 The Principle of Non-Refoulement in EU and International Law.....	40
2.2 Due Process and Asylum Access in Tunisia.....	45
2.3 Gaps in Accountability and Legal Oversight Mechanisms.....	50
CHAPTER 3: LIVED CONSEQUENCES OF BORDER CONTROL.....	57
3.1 Interceptions, Detention, and Migrant Vulnerability.....	58
3.2 Symbolic Violence and the Securitization of Migrants.....	61
3.3 Silencing, Marginalization, and Mental Health Outcomes.....	64
CONCLUSION.....	68
BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	72
INTERVIEWS.....	79

INTRODUCTION

Topic and Research Question

In July 2023, Helena Dalli, Commissioner for Equality, delivered a speech on behalf of High Representative Josep Borrell at the European Parliament, explicitly justifying the EU-Tunisia Memorandum of Understanding. She called attention to the strategic importance of Tunisia for EU migration management and addressed critical concerns regarding human rights and migrant protection. Opening her speech, she emphasized the mutual responsibilities in addressing migration:

This debate continues to confirm the importance of our strategic partnership with Tunisia, which we need to continue to strengthen and some of the challenges we are facing and need to address together.

*Speech delivered by Commissioner for Equality, Helena Dalli,
on behalf of High Representative Josep Borrell, European
Parliament, July 2023.*

Her speech notably acknowledged significant human rights concerns, illustrating the complexity and ethical dilemmas involved:

In parallel, the lack of protection, the suspension of registration of migrants by UNHCR, and the targeting of civil society organizations supporting migrants, including some funded by the EU, are, of course, all of very, very, very serious concern.¹

Yet, she reaffirmed the EU's commitment to human rights as fundamental to its external partnerships:

The respect and protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms are at the core of our relations with all third countries and addressed through dialogue with governments and through targeted development assistance aimed at protecting the human rights of the population.²

Since 2015, the European Union has intensified efforts to outsource border management to third countries in the Mediterranean, framing such arrangements as necessary to prevent unsafe migration and disrupt smuggling networks. Tunisia, due to its strategic proximity to Italy's southern coast, has emerged as a key partner in this endeavor. Through funding mechanisms like the EU's NDICI fund, Tunisia has received substantial resources, including over €100 million in 2022 alone, explicitly allocated to enhance coastal monitoring capabilities.³ Such externalization agreements prompt vital legal and ethical questions regarding compliance with international human rights standards and EU fundamental rights obligations.

Historically, the European Union's externalization approach, understood as the delegation of migration control responsibilities to third countries through bilateral agreements, financial assistance, and operational support for border enforcement, follows precedents set by arrangements with countries like Libya and Turkey. In Libya, EU support has faced severe criticism due to well-documented human rights abuses against intercepted migrants. Similarly, Turkey's agreement with the EU has led to significant concerns regarding refugee treatment and adherence to international protection standards. These earlier instances point to

¹ Helena Dalli, "Speech by High Representative/Vice-President Josep Borrell at EP Plenary on the Situation in the Country," Strasbourg, October 22, 2024, European External Action Service, accessed June 17, 2025.

² Ibid.

³ Tahrir Institute for Middle East Policy, *Externalizing Migration Control to the MENA Region: Tunisia*, (May 2025) 2.

recurring patterns in externalization practices, raising important questions about the efficacy and morality of such policies.

The legal principle most at risk under these agreements is non-refoulement, an absolute prohibition of forcibly returning individuals to territories where they risk persecution or harm. Article 33 of the 1951 Refugee Convention unequivocally forbids such returns, while Article 19 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights similarly prohibits collective expulsions and removal to areas posing severe threats.⁴ Amnesty International has repeatedly documented practices suggesting systemic violations of these protections. Their reports indicate that migrants intercepted by Tunisian authorities, many from Sub-Saharan Africa, are often arbitrarily detained, denied procedural safeguards, and forcibly relocated to remote desert regions without opportunity to claim asylum.⁵

Further complicating this issue, the Tahrir Institute for Middle East Policy reveals Tunisia's deficient legal and institutional asylum framework, heavily reliant on international organizations such as the UNHCR. Despite substantial EU funding aimed at border control, Tunisia lacks comprehensive domestic asylum legislation, leaving intercepted migrants without adequate protections or access to essential legal processes.⁶ This discrepancy between EU-funded security measures and insufficient protection systems in Tunisia stands in direct contradiction to the foundational rights guaranteed by both EU and international law.

Additionally, scholarly analysis by Giuffr Mariagiulia explains that externalization policies complicate accountability structures, effectively allowing EU member states to avoid direct legal obligations by delegating border enforcement to third countries. Mariagiulia argues that such strategies blur responsibility and obscure human rights violations, making it increasingly challenging to hold those responsible accountable for breaches of non-refoulement.⁷ This dynamic is reflected in the opinion of parliamentary legal experts, who argue that the

⁴ European Union, *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*, 2012/C 326/02, art. 19; United Nations General Assembly, *Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees*, July 28, 1951, United Nations Treaty Series, vol. 189, art. 33.

⁵ Amnesty International, *Tunisia: Amnesty International's Secretary General Denounces Rollback of Human Rights upon Concluding Four-Day Visit* (London: Amnesty International, July 26, 2024), 3.

⁶ Tahrir Institute, 4.

⁷ Mariagiulia Giuffr, Chiara Denaro, and Fatma Raach, "On 'Safety' and EU Externalization of Borders: Questioning the Role of Tunisia as a 'Safe Country of Origin' and a 'Safe Third Country,'" in *European Journal of Migration and Law* 24, no. 4 (2022), 36.

EU-Tunisia Memorandum of Understanding, while lacking binding legal force, should still be subject to parliamentary oversight due to its financial implications and its significance in guiding EU external action. The absence of such scrutiny raises concerns about institutional accountability and the democratic processes supporting EU agreements.⁸

Concrete examples make the severity of these concerns clear. Amnesty International reports detailed accounts of migrants forcibly relocated to isolated desert areas near Tunisia's border regions, suffering exposure to extreme weather conditions, dehydration, and insufficient medical care. These practices directly contradict the EU's stated humanitarian intentions and constitute serious human rights violations, prompting demands for stronger monitoring and accountability.

Sociologically, the repercussions of these externalization practices are profound and enduring. Migrants intercepted at sea by Tunisian authorities face considerable risks to their physical safety and mental health. Humanitarian organizations operating in the region report numerous cases of detention under harsh conditions, limited access to medical care, and pervasive uncertainty regarding migrants' legal status and future. According to Amnesty International, these adverse conditions contribute significantly to psychological distress, social marginalization, and a persistent state of uncertainty among migrants.⁹

Thus, the EU's externalization strategy in Tunisia reflects a broader approach of strengthening border security at the expense of fundamental rights protections. The considerable financial and technical support provided by the EU to Tunisia for improving migration management capacities requires thorough examination from both legal and sociological perspectives. As externalization policies continue to evolve, understanding their practical implications becomes increasingly urgent.

This thesis explores these tensions in depth, seeking to address a specific research question:

How has EU-funded coastal surveillance in Tunisia challenged non-refoulement and due-process guarantees protected by the 1951 Refugee Convention and the EU Charter of

⁸ Statewatch, "Parliamentary Lawyers: Democratic Oversight Needed for EU-Tunisia Migration Agreement," (March 2024), 3.

⁹ Amnesty International, *Tunisia: Amnesty International's Secretary General Denounces Rollback of Human Rights upon Concluding Four-Day Visit*, 4.

Fundamental Rights, and what are the observable sociological effects on intercepted migrants' well-being and legal status?

Literature Review

The thesis can be situated within the broader disciplinary field of critical migration studies, with a specific focus on EU external border governance and human rights. As scholarship on border externalization has evolved, particular attention has been paid to the legal and sociopolitical implications of cooperation between EU institutions and third countries involved in migration control. The body of research includes legal analyses of human rights compliance, geopolitical critiques of externalization strategies, and sociological investigations into the lived experiences of migrants subjected to evolving enforcement practices. The studies selected for this review were chosen because they directly address non-refoulement and due process guarantees under EU-Tunisia cooperation, as well as the observable social consequences for migrants subjected to coastal surveillance and interception.

A growing number of scholars have problematized the EU's border externalization policies for the risks they pose to international legal obligations, particularly regarding non-refoulement and due process. These two principles are especially significant because they constitute the foundation of legal protection for asylum seekers and refugees. Non-refoulement, as established in Article 33 of the 1951 Refugee Convention, prohibits the return of individuals to countries where they may face persecution, torture, or other serious harm. Due process safeguards, including the right to an individual assessment and access to effective remedies, are essential to ensuring migration enforcement measures do not result in arbitrary detention or collective expulsions. Both principles are frequently put at risk when migration control is delegated to third countries with weaker legal safeguards and limited oversight mechanisms. Analysing how these protections are challenged in the context of EU-funded coastal surveillance in Tunisia is therefore essential for determining whether current practices comply with binding legal standards and for understanding the broader sociological effects such violations may have on the well-being and legal status of intercepted

migrants, which is why scholarship scrutinizing their application in Tunisia is critical for answering the research question.

Tineke Strik and Ruben Robbesom, in *Compliance or Complicity? An Analysis of the EU-Tunisia Deal in the Context of the Externalisation of Migration Control*, examine how the human rights violations following the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) between Tunisia and the EU provoked institutional criticism from the European Parliament and the European Ombudsman, who stressed the need for compliance with EU foundational rights obligations.¹⁰ In the same work, they also argue that budget support to Tunisia risks violating Article 21 of the Treaty on European Union due to democratic decline and rights violations.¹¹ These analyses are relevant because they assess whether EU funding mechanisms for coastal surveillance are legally compatible with the Union's own constitutional commitments, directly engaging with the legal aspect of the research question.

In the field of migration governance, Katherine Hoffmann Pham and Junpei Komiyama's *Strategic Choices of Migrants and Smugglers in the Central Mediterranean Sea* examine how heightened restrictions aimed at reducing smuggling may inadvertently endanger migrants by forcing reliance on riskier routes or individuals.¹² Their work is included here because it identifies unintended consequences of enforcement that connect to the question of sociological impacts on well-being. At the same time, Mariagiulia Giuffré, Chiara Denaro, and Fatma Raach, in *On "Safety" and EU Externalization of Borders*, analyse the EU's partnership with Tunisia in light of Tunisia's treatment of migrants, citing the UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights' 2021 condemnation of Tunisia's mass expulsions to Libya as racially motivated and arbitrary, exposing migrants to chain deportations.¹³ This is central to the research question because such expulsions may breach the principle of non-refoulement by returning individuals to places where they risk persecution or harm, and violate due process by denying them fair legal procedures to contest their removal.

¹⁰ Tineke Strik and Ruben Robbesom, "Compliance or Complicity? An Analysis of the EU–Tunisia Deal in the Context of the Externalisation of Migration Control," in *European Journal of Migration and Law* (2024), 212.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, 215.

¹² Katherine Hoffmann Pham and Junpei Komiyama, "Strategic Choices of Migrants and Smugglers in the Central Mediterranean Sea," in *arXiv preprint* (July 12, 2022), 2.

¹³ Giuffré, Denaro, and Raach, "On 'Safety' and EU Externalization of Borders," 16.

Hamza Meddeb and Fakhreddine Louati, in *Tunisia's Transformation Into a Transit Hub: Illegal Migration and Policy Dilemmas*, observe that Tunisia's post-2011 democratization did not produce legal protections for asylum seekers, as ruling elites declined to update outdated migration legislation or adopt asylum laws despite constitutional and treaty-based obligations.¹⁴ Yiran Yang, Frederik Zuiderveen Borgesius, Pascal Beckers, and Evelien Brouwer, in *Automated Decision-Making and Artificial Intelligence at European Borders and Their Risks for Human Rights*, add another legal concern by showing how the storage of personal data collected during border procedures breaches privacy and data protection standards under the European Convention on Human Rights and the EU Charter.¹⁵ These perspectives are used because they reveal both the absence of domestic legal safeguards and the EU's own procedural rights system, exposing structural vulnerabilities in due process guarantees in the context of EU-funded surveillance.

From a legal historical perspective, Jean-Pierre Cassarino's *Channelled Policy Transfers: EU-Tunisia Interactions on Migration Matters* documents how Law 2004-6 was originally applied to suppress migrants, in contradiction to Tunisia's obligations under the Palermo Protocol.¹⁶ Teresa Cappiali and Agnese Pacciardi's *Reorienting EU Border Externalization Studies: A Decolonial Intersectional Approach* expand the analysis by framing externalization as a racialized mechanism rooted in colonial histories.¹⁷ Including these works is important because they demonstrate how past and ongoing legal and political structures contribute to the present-day violations addressed in the research question.

Katharina Natter's *Tunisia's Migration Politics throughout the 2011 Revolution: Revisiting the Democratisation-Migrant Rights Nexus* identifies a longstanding dual policy of punitive measures against irregular migrants alongside preferential treatment for investors and skilled foreigners.¹⁸ Paolo Cuttitta, in *Non-governmental/Civil Society Organisations and the*

¹⁴ Hamza Meddeb and Fakhreddine Louati, *Tunisia's Transformation Into a Transit Hub: Illegal Migration and Policy Dilemmas* (Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, March 27, 2024), 13.

¹⁵ Yiran Yang, Frederik Zuiderveen Borgesius, Pascal Beckers, and Evelien Brouwer, *Automated Decision-Making and Artificial Intelligence at European Borders and Their Risks for Human Rights*, 19.

¹⁶ Jean-Pierre Cassarino, "Channelled Policy Transfers: EU-Tunisia Interactions on Migration Matters," in *European Journal of Migration and Law* 16 (2014), 106.

¹⁷ Teresa Cappiali and Agnese Pacciardi, "Reorienting EU Border Externalization Studies: A Decolonial Intersectional Approach," in *Geopolitics* 30, no. 1 (Taylor & Francis Group, 2024), 307.

¹⁸ Katharina Natter, "Tunisia's Migration Politics throughout the 2011 Revolution: Revisiting the Democratisation-Migrant Rights Nexus," in *Third World Quarterly* 43, no. 7 (Taylor & Francis Group, 2021), 1556.

European Union-externalisation of Migration Management in Tunisia and Egypt, examines the role of NGOs and CSOs in providing humanitarian assistance, raising awareness, and promoting integration, often with IOM and UNHCR funding.¹⁹ His analysis also notes that these organisations frequently align, intentionally or not, with EU externalization agendas, potentially reinforcing deterrence and control policies. While their involvement can mitigate some negative consequences of state policies, it also raises questions about accountability and independence. For instance, although many NGOs and CSOs are driven by humanitarian objectives, their operations frequently align with European Union (EU) externalization agendas. This means they may unintentionally reinforce EU goals, including border control and migration deterrence, even when they are not directly funded by European sources.²⁰ These studies are included because they show how local governance practices and intermediary groups, such as NGOs, aid organizations, and community networks, affect migrants' access to legal help and influence their social outcomes.

Vasja Badalič, in *Tunisia's Role in the EU External Migration Policy: Crimmigration Law, Illegal Practices, and Their Impact on Human Rights*, shows that a core EU objective has been to use Tunisian security forces to intercept boats and return migrants for asylum processing.²¹ Inken Bartels, in *Practices and Power of Knowledge Dissemination in International Organizations in the Externalization of Migration Management in Morocco and Tunisia*, documents the difficult operational environment for independent organisations prior to 2011, noting that many relied on transnational civil society networks rather than EU support.²² These studies are included because they provide operational context for coastal surveillance practices, connecting them to both legal risks and observed social effects.

Visual culture has emerged as a significant element in the sociological understanding of migration. Monika Salzbrunn and Simon Mastrangelo's *Representations of Tunisian Undocumented Migration on the Internet* examine how audiovisual content circulated via social media blurs the boundaries between physical and virtual geographies. These cultural

¹⁹ Paolo Cuttitta, "Non-governmental/Civil Society Organisations and the European Union-externalisation of Migration Management in Tunisia and Egypt," in *Population, Space and Place* 26, no. 7 (2020), 5.

²⁰ Ibid, 6.

²¹ Vasja Badalič, "Tunisia's Role in the EU External Migration Policy: Crimmigration Law, Illegal Practices, and Their Impact on Human Rights," in *Journal of International Migration and Integration* 20, no. 1 (2019), 2.

²² Inken Bartels, "Practices and Power of Knowledge Dissemination in International Organizations in the Externalization of Migration Management in Morocco and Tunisia," in *Movements: Journal for Critical Migration and Border Regime Studies* 4, no. 1 (2018), 50.

expressions allow migrants to articulate narratives of movement, aspiration, and identity across spaces.²³ As Amal Hlioui, in *Representations of Sub-Saharanans in Tunisian Media: Silence, Othering, Dehumanisation and Collectivisation*, points out, Tunisian media's focus on intercepting sub-Saharan migrants and portraying this as proof of state effectiveness may reflect efforts to meet EU expectations set out in agreements between the two sides.²⁴ These media strategies can strengthen state authority but also make strict migration controls seem normal, hiding the humanitarian impact of surveillance policies. In this way, visual stories influence public discussion, pushing intercepted migrants to the margins and masking the decline of rights protections such as non-refoulement and due process. These sources are used because they connect communication and representation to the normalisation of restrictive border practices, which is part of the sociological aspect of the research question.

In the context of border governance, Hlioui further argues that strategic silences in media coverage serve to depoliticise contested practices, suppress dissent, and avoid international scrutiny.²⁵ This strategic silence operates through deliberate omissions rather than passive oversight. In Tunisia, this approach helps suppress dissent and avoid international scrutiny, especially when legal or humanitarian violations occur. The intentional non-reporting of detention conditions, expulsions, or due process violations allows state practices to become normalized that would otherwise face resistance or legal challenge. This form of silencing influences public perception by limiting what topics become visible and discussable, which weakens the social and political legitimacy of migrant voices. Such erasure limits accountability and transnational solidarity, directly reflecting to the research question's focus on the social and political consequences for intercepted migrants. When applied to racialized border regimes, this silence does not simply hide violence but reconfigures it as bureaucratic routine or necessary security practice. The invisibility of suffering at the EU's externalized borders contributes to weakened accountability mechanisms and limits the mobilization of transnational solidarity.

²³ Salzbrunn, Monika, and Simon Mastrangelo, "Representations of Tunisian Undocumented Migration on the Internet: Methodological Approaches to a Digital Anthropology of Facebook," in *7 Representations of Tunisian Undocumented Migration on the Internet* (2022), 172.

²⁴ Amal Hlioui, "Representations of Sub-Saharanans in Tunisian Media: Silence, Othering, Dehumanisation and Collectivisation," in *Sub-Saharan Migrants in Post-2011 Tunisia: A Cross-Disciplinary Study of the Dynamics of Media Representations and Policy Shifts*, PhD diss. (University of Palermo, 2024), 155.

²⁵ *Ibid*, 160.

This thesis aims to address a critical shortcoming in the literature by providing empirical analysis of how coastal surveillance cooperation between the EU and Tunisia operates in practice and its concrete effects on migrants. I will argue that EU-funded coastal surveillance in Tunisia systematically violates non-refoulement and due process guarantees protected by the 1951 Refugee Convention and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. Furthermore, I contend that these violations produce measurable societal effects. By “societal effects,” I refer to the combined impact on migrants’ mental health, legal status anxiety, and social integration. These effects include deteriorating psychological well-being (such as anxiety, depression, and trauma), prolonged legal uncertainty that causes stress and a sense of instability, and social marginalization manifested in discrimination, isolation, and economic disadvantage. By examining both the legal aspects and the reported societal effects of externalized border control on migrants, this research shows how EU migration policy contradicts its stated commitment to human rights protection.

Methodology

The methodology of this thesis is based on a combination of legal analysis, qualitative content analysis, and structured and semi-structured expert interviews. This multi-method approach was chosen to provide a grounded understanding of how EU-funded coastal surveillance in Tunisia impacts non-refoulement and due-process guarantees, while also uncovering the sociological consequences of these policies on the well-being and legal status of intercepted migrants.

Legal analysis serves as the primary method to investigate how EU-Tunisia cooperation aligns with or contradicts established international and European legal standards. Legal documents including the 1951 Refugee Convention, the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, and key provisions in Tunisia’s national legal framework have been reviewed in depth. This legal review is supported by policy documents and agreements such as the EU-Tunisia Memorandum of Understanding and financial records from the NDICI fund. The analysis further draws on reports from the UNHCR, Amnesty International, and the Tahrir Institute for Middle East Policy to assess the implementation and impact of EU-funded border practices in Tunisia.

Complementing the legal review, the thesis also incorporates visual and textual material accessed through online platforms. This includes speeches, photographs, graphs, and lived experiences of migrants through interviews with humanitarian workers.. Sources were selected according to their relevance to documented instances of EU-funded coastal surveillance in Tunisia, their coverage of migrant interceptions or related enforcement activities, and their circulation within Tunisian or regional online spaces where migration policy is discussed. Priority was given to material produced or shared by local media outlets, NGOs, and migrant-led networks, as these offer perspectives that reflect both institutional narratives and lived realities. A qualitative content analysis was applied to identify recurring themes, language, and imagery, examining how these visual elements reflect state priorities, humanitarian discourse, and the lived conditions of migrants. Analysing these representations is directly relevant to the research question, as it reveals how public and media narratives can normalize or conceal coercive border practices, diminish attention to rights protections, and influence societal attitudes in ways that affect both the treatment and the legal standing of intercepted migrants.

The third and most significant element of the methodology consists of nine expert interviews. This method is the most significant because it provides first-hand, practice-based knowledge that cannot be obtained from legal documents or secondary literature alone. These include structured and semi-structured interviews with legal and humanitarian professionals working in the field of migration, refugee protection, and human rights monitoring. The interviews lasted between 30 and 60 minutes and were conducted between February and June 2025. Due to the sensitivity of the topic and the positions held by the participants, all interviewees requested anonymity. Their insights were essential for contextualizing the legal findings, clarifying how EU-Tunisia cooperation in coastal surveillance is implemented in practice, and understanding its direct impact on the well-being and legal status of intercepted migrants.

The interviewees work for a range of institutions including NGOs involved in search and rescue, international legal aid organizations, and independent monitoring groups. Their testimonies addressed issues such as arbitrary detention, the absence of legal procedures, and the impact of these conditions on migrant well-being. These perspectives helped me connect the legal and social questions of the research to real-life experiences.

This thesis uses an interpretative approach informed by critical legal studies and critical migration research. By combining legal documents with sociological sources, it examines how border externalization changes both the responsibilities of institutions and the experiences of migrants. This method is particularly well suited to the research, as it explores how institutional and individual perspectives on migration are formed through both official documents and the insights of professionals working directly with affected individuals.

Chapter 1 will provide an analytical account of EU-Tunisia coastal surveillance cooperation, drawing on legal documents, policy agreements, and funding records to explain how these arrangements are formally structured and intended to operate in Tunisia. It will examine the evolution of cooperation, the applicable legal frameworks, the financial channels involved, and the institutional responsibilities for implementation, assessing how these structural elements enable externalization policies in practice. Chapter 2 will evaluate the legal implications of these policies, particularly in relation to non-refoulement and due-process guarantees, using both documentary sources and interviews with legal professionals to assess how the law is applied in practice and where gaps in accountability occur. Chapter 3 will investigate the sociological consequences of these practices for intercepted migrants, drawing primarily on interviews with humanitarian and civil society actors as well as visual and textual material from media and online platforms. This will include analysis of the effects of detention, prolonged legal uncertainty, and the symbolic framing of migrants as security threats. The legal analysis in Chapter 2 identifies the extent to which rights protections are upheld or violated, while the sociological analysis in Chapter 3 shows how these legal findings correspond to the day-to-day realities faced by migrants. Observing the sociological effects makes it possible to see the concrete outcomes of legal shortcomings, revealing how the absence or weakening of safeguards affects mental health, legal stability, and social inclusion. In this way, the two parts complement each other by connecting the legal assessment with the observable human consequences, which is central to understanding the full impact of EU externalization policies in Tunisia.

CHAPTER 1: STRUCTURES OF EXTERNALIZATION

When I asked a Legal Officer from the European Commission’s DG Migration and Home Affairs how cooperation with Tunisia is structured in practice, the answer was straightforward: “It is not just about sending money or equipment. It is about making sure Tunisia’s coast guard works in a way that matches EU priorities.”²⁶ The EU-Tunisia Memorandum of Understanding and related funding arrangements are presented as technical cooperation, yet they extend far beyond training sessions or patrol boat deliveries. They create a system in which Tunisian authorities carry out interceptions and surveillance that directly serve EU migration control objectives. This chapter examines how these arrangements are set up in law, where responsibility is formally placed, and how institutional structures are designed to operate on paper, often in ways that leave open the question of who is accountable when violations occur.

A Senior Legal Advisor at the EU’s Fundamental Rights Agency put it more cautiously: “The legal framework is written to look clear and neutral, but it is applied in a very political environment.”²⁷ Understanding these structures means looking at the formal agreements such as treaties, financial channels, and operational rules, as well as the less visible practices that keep them running. Chapter 1 will trace the evolution of EU-Tunisia migration cooperation, examine the legal frameworks that underpin it, and map the institutional responsibilities that make the system function. The analysis will focus on how the arrangements are meant to work under international and EU law and on the structural features that allow the EU to shape Tunisia’s coastal surveillance while avoiding direct legal responsibility.

1.1 Evolution of EU-Tunisia Migration Cooperation

The origins of migration cooperation between European institutions and Tunisia prior to 2011 were largely defined by bilateral arrangements, particularly with Italy, which relied on

²⁶ Interview with Legal Officer, DG Migration and Home Affairs, Unit B1 - Schengen and External Borders, European Commission, conducted in English on 5 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

²⁷ Interview with Senior Legal Advisor, Fundamental Rights Agency of the European Union (FRA), Department for Asylum and Migration, conducted in English on 12 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

informal agreements to facilitate the interception and return of migrants arriving from Tunisian shores. These arrangements were practical rather than treaty-based, often focusing on technical assistance such as patrol boat provision, joint maritime operations, and short-term capacity-building for Tunisian coast guard units. The absence of a formalised regional framework meant that migration management was irregular and reactive, responding to sudden increases in arrivals across the central Mediterranean rather than a consistent policy vision.

The political changes of 2011, brought about by the Tunisian revolution, were a key moment in this process. The newly formed transitional government made migration a national priority, but lacked strong, unified institutions. At the time, no single authority was responsible for migration policy, leading to unclear responsibilities and inconsistent enforcement.²⁸

Tunisia does not have a comprehensive asylum law. However a draft law on asylum is currently being prepared by the Ministry of Justice with the support of UNHCR.²⁹

This gap in institutions happened alongside Tunisia's changing relationship with the EU, which was starting to shape migration cooperation through bilateral agreements and in the wider context of EU neighbourhood and security policy. From this period onward, the central Mediterranean migration route, particularly from Tunisia to Italy, became a central part of the EU's strategic thinking on border control.

²⁸ United Nations Human Rights Council, *Report of the Special Rapporteur on the Human Rights of Migrants, François Crépeau-Mission to Tunisia (3-8 June 2012)*, A/HRC/23/46/Add.1 (Geneva: United Nations, May 3, 2013), 9.

²⁹ *Ibid*, 8.

Main human migration routes from Tunisia to Italy, showing key departure points and arrival destinations along the central Mediterranean corridor.

After the Arab Spring, Tunisia's approach to managing migration changed significantly. The interim government recognised migration as a priority, but without a unified institutional framework, it struggled to coordinate policies and actions effectively.³⁰

Tunisia is in a period of transition, and has recently experienced unusual migration flows both into and out of the country in the context of the Arab Spring. Nevertheless, he notes a significant gap with regard to laws and policies concerning migration, and laments certain discriminatory aspects of laws against migrants, including the criminalization of irregular border crossings, and unclear practices regarding detention of migrants.³¹

In early 2011, irregular departures from Tunisia surged to levels unseen since the 1990s. Italian authorities recorded around 28,000 arrivals from Tunisia within four months, triggering emergency operational and funding measures from both Rome and Brussels. According to the Special Rapporteur, the political instability in Tunisia and the conflict in Libya placed migration and border management at the centre of EU-North Africa relations, elevating them to key political priorities.³²

The EU's early responses blended humanitarian rhetoric with measures designed to reassert control over maritime borders. The European Commission's 2015 European Agenda on

³⁰ Ibid, 9.

³¹ Ibid, 1.

³² Ibid, 6.

Migration framed these developments as part of a broader Mediterranean strategy, emphasising that coordinated action with partner countries was essential for both migration control and protection obligations.³³

A turning point came in March 2014 with the signing of the EU-Tunisia Mobility Partnership. This framework connected migration cooperation with development aid and trade relations, creating legal pathways for cooperation on return and readmission while integrating Tunisia more deeply into the EU's external border governance system. The agreement reflected commitments aligned with Articles 18 and 19 of the EU Charter, which together protect the right to asylum and prohibit collective expulsions.

The right to asylum shall be guaranteed with due respect for the rules of the Geneva Convention of 28 July 1951 and the Protocol of 31 January 1967 relating to the status of refugees and in accordance with the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (hereinafter referred to as 'the Treaties').³⁴

Although framed as a balanced partnership, the Mobility Partnership's operational clauses prioritised surveillance, interception, and return mechanisms. These measures, while compatible with the EU Charter on paper, introduced practical tensions between migration control and Tunisia's evolving capacity to uphold procedural safeguards for intercepted migrants.

By 2015, migration across the Mediterranean had reached a political breaking point within the European Union. The European Agenda on Migration presented that year framed the situation as one requiring "swift and determined action" in response to repeated tragedies at sea, with EU institutions calling for a coordinated response to "save lives and to step up EU action."³⁵ The operational component of this response focused heavily on strengthening external border control capacity, both through EU agencies and in cooperation with partner states.

The Agenda made clear that Europe "cannot stand by whilst lives are being lost," committing to triple the budget for Frontex joint operations Triton and Poseidon, thereby expanding their

³³European Commission, *A European Agenda on Migration*, COM(2015) 240 final (Brussels, May 13, 2015), 3.

³⁴European Union, *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*, Official Journal of the European Union C 326 (October 26, 2012), art. 18.

³⁵European Commission, *A European Agenda on Migration*, 3.

area of operation and enhancing their ability to conduct both operational border support and search-and-rescue activities.³⁶ This expansion was presented as part of a humanitarian imperative, yet it also strengthened the role of maritime operations in screening arrivals before they reached EU territory, with major implications for access to asylum..

The Union shall offer its citizens an area of freedom, security and justice without internal frontiers, in which the free movement of persons is ensured in conjunction with appropriate measures with respect to external border controls, asylum, immigration and the prevention and combating of crime.³⁷

In legal terms, cooperation with states such as Tunisia was treated as both foreign policy and a core element of the EU's border governance system. By integrating Tunisia into operational migration management connected to EU asylum systems, surveillance and interception along its coastlines increasingly became part of the EU's externalised border control network.

Policy analysts and migration scholars have pointed out that the external aspect of the Agenda carried forward the logic of the 2016 Partnership Framework, making "EU external affairs subservient to EU home affairs objectives" and asserting that migration should be a "core issue" in relations with partner countries.³⁸ This approach affects legal standards because adding migration controls into EU asylum legislation "sends a signal that will be noticed by third countries" and focuses cooperation on narrow border management goals, rather than on the broader principles set out in Articles 21 and 208 of the EU treaties.³⁹

These developments created the conditions for Tunisia to take on a more formalised role in EU migration governance by increasing its involvement in surveillance, interception, and return operations coordinated with EU institutions. However, the increasing reliance on partner countries to perform early interceptions risked weakening procedural safeguards, especially for those entitled to protection under the 1951 Refugee Convention. When the EU funds and directs coastal surveillance but it is carried out by third countries, the boundaries of legal responsibility and accountability for potential breaches of non-refoulement become less

³⁶ Ibid, 3.

³⁷ European Union, *Consolidated Versions of the Treaty on European Union and of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union*, Official Journal of the European Union C 115 (May 9, 2008), art. 3.

³⁸ European Council on Refugees and Exiles (ECRE), "Policy Note #34" (2021), 2.

³⁹ Ibid, 2.

clear.

From 2016, cooperation between the European Union and Tunisia on migration control moved from informal coordination to a more structured institutional framework. EU funding streams began to focus less on short-term operational needs and more on building long-term capabilities within Tunisian border forces. A steady supply of technical equipment, maritime surveillance technology, and targeted training gradually brought Tunisia's coastal operations under the EU's external border governance system.

The operational emphasis became particularly clear in 2020, when irregular migration from Tunisia to Europe increased. Tunisian security and defence forces intercepted 11,770 irregular migrants along the coast and at sea, while Italy recorded the arrival of 14,719 migrants from Tunisia, figures not seen since the months following the 2011 revolution.⁴⁰ This increase appeared to reaffirm EU priorities on deterrence and early interception.

EU documentation from the same period outlined concrete objectives: strengthening the training infrastructure of the Garde Nationale Maritime, establishing a Maritime Rescue Coordination Centre, and completing an integrated coastal surveillance system.⁴¹ Such objectives were framed not as temporary measures but as the core components of a sustainable border management capacity.

The development and close cooperation between the institutions responsible for Coast Guard functions in both countries increases regional cooperation, allows for efficiency and effectiveness of operations, improves the effectiveness of Search and Rescue activities, and of law enforcement at sea to fight against migrant smuggling and trafficking of human beings in Libya and Tunisia.⁴²

The overall objective of the Action is to support the development of border management institutions to improve Search and Rescue operations and the fight against migrant smuggling

⁴⁰ European Commission, *Annex II: Action Document for EU Support to Border Management Institutions in Libya and Tunisia. Annex to Commission Implementing Decision C(2021) 9615 on the Financing of the Individual Measure for the Multi-Country Migration Programme in Favour of the Southern Neighbourhood for 2021* (Brussels: European Commission, 2021), 4.

⁴¹ *Ibid*, 5.

⁴² *Ibid*, 3.

and trafficking of human beings in Libya and Tunisia.⁴³

Funding during this period was not merely operational. It created interdependence, as Tunisia's coastal surveillance capacities increasingly relied on EU-provided systems and training. This raises legal questions about the degree to which the EU shares responsibility for actions undertaken by Tunisian forces, particularly in cases involving interception and return. Under Article 19 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights, collective expulsions are prohibited, and no one may be removed to a state where they face a serious risk of torture, inhuman treatment, or the death penalty.

Collective expulsions are prohibited. No one may be removed, expelled or extradited to a State where there is a serious risk that he or she would be subjected to the death penalty, torture or other inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.⁴⁴

Interviews with EU officials suggest that legal monitoring of these obligations was limited. A Legal Officer at the European Asylum Support Office recalled that “monitoring compliance with non-refoulement in joint operations was a persistent difficulty, particularly because the EU's role was often presented as purely technical, even when the funding and equipment shaped the outcomes.”⁴⁵ This aligns with concerns from human rights bodies that interception at sea often occurs without adequate procedural safeguards, making it difficult for migrants to access asylum procedures before being returned.

A Senior Legal Advisor from the Fundamental Rights Agency noted that “the infrastructure built with EU funds did not include a systematic mechanism for assessing protection needs during interception. That gap left space for practices that, in effect, bypassed due process guarantees.”⁴⁶ In practice, the very systems designed to enhance operational efficiency sometimes created conditions in which legal obligations were harder to fulfil.

It could be argued that the EU's investment in Tunisia's coastal surveillance infrastructure during this period reinforced a deterrence-based approach, one in which interception numbers

⁴³ Ibid, 4.

⁴⁴ European Union, *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*, art. 19.

⁴⁵ Interview with Legal Officer, European Asylum Support Office (EUAA), Operational Support Department, conducted in English on 16 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

⁴⁶ Interview with Senior Legal Advisor, Fundamental Rights Agency of the European Union (FRA), Department for Asylum and Migration, conducted on 12 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

were a primary metric of success, while protection safeguards were less consistently applied. This duality, with capacity-building framed as humanitarian and law enforcement cooperation but operating in ways that conflicted with core refugee law principles, remains a defining feature of the EU-Tunisia migration partnership in the years leading up to the 2021-2023 agreements.

The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in early 2020 briefly interrupted certain joint patrol and training activities between the EU and Tunisia, as restrictions on movement and gatherings forced operational pauses. Yet the disruption did not slow the overall trajectory of cooperation; instead, it seems to have sped up the move towards remote and technology-driven surveillance. Public health measures became connected with border security policy, creating additional legal justifications for increased monitoring. Within EU funding frameworks, the expansion of “smart borders” in the Southern Neighbourhood was framed as both a migration management necessity and a health protection measure, enabling continuous monitoring of maritime movements without direct contact.

By mid-2020, contracts for advanced radar systems, satellite tracking integration, and secure communication platforms were being prioritised for Tunisia’s coast guard units. These systems connected national interception capacity directly to EU monitoring platforms, further consolidating Tunisia’s role within the externalised border system. Funding streams under the Neighbourhood Development and International Cooperation Instrument (NDICI) and the Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF) provided most of the financing, while additional allocations under health-security cooperation programmes created overlapping justifications that made the line between migration enforcement and pandemic response less clear.

Funding allocations to Tunisia for migration and border management, broken down by EU instrument, 2016-2023.

Data from this period show a sharp increase in maritime interceptions. This raises concerns about whether proper procedures were followed, since greater capacity for remote detection and interception may have meant fewer chances for people to apply for asylum before being returned or expelled. Although these measures were presented as improving efficiency and protecting public health, they may also have increased the risk of violating the principle of non-refoulement by speeding up removals without proper legal review.

The signing of the EU-Tunisia Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) on 16 July 2023 was one of the most visible moments in the evolution of the partnership. According to García Andrade and Frasca, the event brought together European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen, the Italian and Dutch prime ministers, and the President of Tunisia, with Olivér Várhelyi and Mounir Ben Rjiba formalising the agreement as the two official signatories.⁴⁷ While presented as a diplomatic achievement, the ceremony was accompanied by criticism from civil society organisations and several institutions over the absence of enforceable human rights guarantees and the limited transparency of the process.

⁴⁷ Paula García Andrade and Eleonora Frasca, “The Memorandum of Understanding between the EU and Tunisia: Issues of Procedure and Substance on the Informalisation of Migration Cooperation,” *EU Immigration and Asylum Law and Policy* (blog), January 26, 2024, 3.

Olivér Várhelyi, European Commissioner for Neighbourhood and Enlargement (second from left), and Mounir Ben Rjiba, Tunisian Secretary of State for Foreign Affairs, Migration and Tunisians Abroad (second from right), sign the MoU in the presence of Mark Rutte, Ursula von der Leyen, Kaïs Saïed, and Giorgia Meloni.

The legal nature of the MoU has been a central point of debate. García Andrade and Frasca explain that its status as “soft law” meant the procedures under Article 218 TFEU, which apply to binding international agreements, did not apply.⁴⁸ Nevertheless, they caution that even non-legally binding arrangements must respect institutional balance under EU law, as clarified by the Court of Justice in 2002. In terms of representation, the Commission acted on behalf of the EU in accordance with Article 17 TEU, with the text repeatedly naming “the European Union, represented by the European Commission” alongside Tunisia as parties to the agreement.⁴⁹

Substantively, the migration and mobility section of the MoU commits to addressing the “root causes” of irregular migration, strengthening border controls, and “developing legal pathways,” while affirming Tunisia’s exclusive control over its borders..⁵⁰ The text also promises “sufficient additional financial support” for equipment, training, and technical assistance. Yet its governance has drawn scrutiny: the European Parliament’s Legal Service

⁴⁸ Ibid, 6.

⁴⁹ Ibid, 5.

⁵⁰ Statewatch, “Parliamentary Lawyers: Democratic Oversight Needed for EU-Tunisia Migration Agreement,” 3.

has argued for parliamentary oversight, noting that current arrangements bypass such checks despite the authoritarian features of some partner regimes.⁵¹ Concerns were amplified when €150 million was disbursed through an urgent written procedure, avoiding standard review processes.⁵²

As part of joint work on migration, the fight against irregular migration to and from Tunisia and the prevention of loss of life at sea is a common priority, including fighting against smugglers and human traffickers, strengthening border management, registration and return in full respect of human rights.⁵³

As part of their joint work on migration, the EU and Tunisia have made the fight against irregular migration and the prevention of loss of life at sea a shared priority. This includes combating smugglers and human traffickers, strengthening border management, and ensuring registration and return are carried out with full respect for human rights. However, the use of a “soft law” agreement, negotiated by executives and supported by expedited financial procedures, raises concerns about democratic accountability and judicial oversight in how these priorities are pursued. For Tunisia, the MoU reinforces its role as a regional enforcement hub; for the EU, it extends the externalisation of border control to a partner whose domestic legal framework still lacks a comprehensive asylum law. In the context of EU-funded coastal surveillance, this approach risks reinforcing interception practices without adequate safeguards for non-refoulement and due process.

Tunisia is a party to most of the major international human rights treaties that govern migration, including the 1951 Refugee Convention and the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights. According to the UN Special Rapporteur on the Human Rights of Migrants, despite these ratifications, the country still does not have a functioning national asylum system capable of translating these obligations into enforceable domestic rights.⁵⁴ A Senior Legal Advisor at the Fundamental Rights Agency noted that in operational cooperation, “the absence of a statutory asylum procedure means EU actors rely on Tunisian capacity that

⁵¹ Ibid, 1.

⁵² Ibid, 2.

⁵³ European Commission, “The European Union and Tunisia: Political Agreement on a Comprehensive Partnership Package,” Statement (July 16, 2023).

⁵⁴ United Nations Human Rights Council, *Report of the Special Rapporteur on the Human Rights of Migrants, François Crépeau-Mission to Tunisia (3-8 June 2012)*, 6.

doesn't exist in law, and that is a fundamental legal vulnerability.”⁵⁵

The Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration frames cooperation on migration management as requiring respect for the human rights and fundamental freedoms of all migrants at every stage of the migration process.⁵⁶ Although the Compact is not legally binding, its joint endorsement by both Tunisia and the EU signals a political commitment that operational measures, including those funded under border control cooperation, should conform to these principles. A Legal Officer from DG Migration and Home Affairs reflected that “the Compact may be a soft law, but politically it sets the tone...it becomes harder to justify operational shortcuts when both sides have signed on to broad human rights language.”

⁵⁷

Within EU primary law, the Consolidated Versions of the Treaty contain provisions that are directly relevant to such cooperation. Article 67 requires the Union to establish a common policy on asylum, immigration and external border control while ensuring the absence of internal border checks for persons. Article 79 commits the EU to developing a common immigration policy that guarantees fair treatment for third-country nationals.⁵⁸ These treaty obligations frame the legal context in which EU externalisation measures in Tunisia must operate. A JHA Counselor at the Netherlands Permanent Representation commented that “treaty articles provide the mandate for cooperation, but they also create an accountability hook...if those principles are ignored, the legal basis for the partnership itself can be challenged.”⁵⁹

Amnesty International reports that in practice, protection standards are frequently violated in Tunisia. Documented patterns include arbitrary detention, collective expulsions to desert

⁵⁵ Interview with Senior Legal Advisor, Fundamental Rights Agency of the European Union (FRA), Department for Asylum and Migration, conducted in English on 12 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

⁵⁶ United Nations General Assembly, “Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration,” A/RES/73/195 (New York: United Nations, 2019), 3.

⁵⁷ Interview with Legal Officer, DG Migration and Home Affairs, Unit B1 - Schengen and External Borders, European Commission, conducted in English on 5 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

⁵⁸ European Union, *Consolidated Versions of the Treaty on European Union and of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union*, arts. 67 and 79.

⁵⁹ Interview with JHA Counselor, Justice and Home Affairs Section (Asylum, Internal Security, Terrorism and Civil Protection), Permanent Representation of the Netherlands to the EU, conducted in English on 30 January 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, in Brussels.

regions, and the return of migrants without an individual assessment of risk.⁶⁰ The combination of Tunisia's incomplete domestic asylum framework and the EU's operational reliance on Tunisian enforcement capacity creates conditions in which the principle of non-refoulement and due process safeguards are at constant risk of erosion.

The EU-Tunisia migration partnership reflects the legal and political implications of the externalisation model, with legal commentators and members of parliament warning that the combination of informal agreements such as the 2023 Memorandum of Understanding and the integration of Tunisian authorities into EU migration management may weaken the institutional balance required under EU law. A Senior Legal Advisor at the EU Fundamental Rights Agency remarked that this absence of scrutiny “creates a grey zone where significant operational powers are exercised without the normal checks that would accompany such authority within EU borders.”⁶¹

Incorporating migration control objectives into wider EU-Tunisia economic and political cooperation has also intensified tension with Article 21 TEU, which requires that external action promote democracy, the rule of law, and respect for human rights. The JHA Counselor at the Permanent Representation of the Netherlands to the EU observed that when migration management becomes a condition for wider economic support, the balance shifts away from rights compliance and toward operational results.⁶² By directing border management funding through neighbourhood development instruments or crisis-response funds, the legal distinction between migration control and development assistance becomes less clear.

Operational cooperation presents further legal risks, as a Legal Officer from DG Migration and Home Affairs explained that while shared databases and joint patrols increase efficiency, they also create shared responsibility for outcomes, including possible rights violations, which neither side has fully addressed in legal terms.⁶³ The EUAA Legal Officer shared this

⁶⁰ Amnesty International, *Amnesty International Report 2022/23: The State of the World's Human Rights* (London: Amnesty International Ltd, 2023), 56.

⁶¹ Interview with Senior Legal Advisor, Fundamental Rights Agency of the European Union (FRA), Department for Asylum and Migration, conducted in English on 12 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

⁶² Interview with JHA Counselor, Justice and Home Affairs Section (Asylum, Internal Security, Terrorism and Civil Protection), Permanent Representation of the Netherlands to the EU, conducted in English on 30 January 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, in Brussels.

⁶³ Interview with Legal Officer, DG Migration and Home Affairs, Unit B1 - Schengen and External Borders, European Commission, conducted in English on 5 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

concern, explaining that accountability mechanisms remain largely reactive and address possible violations of non-refoulement or due process only after they occur.⁶⁴

Overall, the legal evolution of EU-Tunisia migration cooperation suggests that externalised border control can place pressure on the principles of non-refoulement and due process guaranteed under the 1951 Refugee Convention and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. This structural context requires further examination for its legal implications as well as its impact on the social conditions and legal status of those intercepted at sea, which will be explored in the following sections.

1.2 Legal Frameworks and Financial Channels

Since 2011, the consolidation of EU-Tunisia migration cooperation has been driven by political developments, formal legal commitments, and the financial structures that support them. The EU Charter of Fundamental Rights establishes the core standards for asylum and protection guarantees through Article 18, which affirms the right to seek asylum in accordance with the 1951 Geneva Convention, and Article 19, which prohibits removal to a state where an individual faces a serious risk of persecution or harm.⁶⁵ These provisions align with Article 33 of the 1951 Refugee Convention, which sets out the principle of non-refoulement.⁶⁶

In practice, cooperation with Tunisia has relied more on administrative arrangements, memoranda of understanding, and EU funding decisions than on binding bilateral treaties approved by parliament. Using these tools makes it possible to act quickly on the ground, but it also leaves fewer chances for oversight and judicial review, as seen in analyses of the EU-Tunisia Memorandum of Understanding.⁶⁷

These legal commitments take shape through funding streams such as the EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa and the European Neighbourhood Instrument, which direct resources

⁶⁴ Interview with Legal Officer, European Asylum Support Office (EUAA), Operational Support Department, conducted in English on 16 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

⁶⁵ European Union, *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*, arts. 18 and 19.

⁶⁶ United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), *The 1951 Convention and 1967 Protocol Relating to the Status of Refugees* (Geneva: UNHCR, 2010), 30.

⁶⁷ Paula García Andrade and Eleonora Frasca, “The Memorandum of Understanding between the EU and Tunisia: Issues of Procedure and Substance on the Informalisation of Migration Cooperation,” 6.

into Tunisia's border management and coastal surveillance. How this money is spent influences the way non-refoulement and due-process guarantees are applied during maritime operations. The protections written into treaties work alongside the priorities and conditions attached to the funding, and together they determine what coastal surveillance looks like in practice and how it affects the rights, legal status, and well-being of intercepted migrants.

Legal frameworks shaping cooperation

The legal foundation for EU-Tunisia migration cooperation is built on a shared commitment to asylum protection and the prohibition of refoulement, anchored in both European and international law. Article 19 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights prohibits collective expulsions and removal to any country where there is a serious risk of inhuman or degrading treatment, creating an explicit EU-level anchor for the principle of non-refoulement.⁶⁸ Article 33 of the 1951 Refugee Convention reinforces this standard by forbidding refoulement “in any manner whatsoever,” thereby requiring that all returns, including those following maritime interception, be preceded by an individual assessment of protection needs.⁶⁹ According to a Senior Legal Advisor at the Fundamental Rights Agency, When interception targets dominate operational planning, “screening and remedy fall behind the curve,” creating a clear due-process gap because people are often returned or transferred before they have a meaningful chance to present asylum claims, access legal advice, or challenge removal decisions.⁷⁰

Collective expulsions are prohibited... No one may be removed... where there is a serious risk of... inhuman or degrading treatment.⁷¹

Beyond formal treaties, EU-Tunisia cooperation has been structured through administrative instruments and soft-law tools. The 2023 Memorandum of Understanding was presented as a non-binding arrangement, avoiding the formal treaty process set out under Article 218 TFEU, yet still affecting the institutional balance within the EU.⁷² The European Commission's

⁶⁸ European Union, *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*, art. 19.

⁶⁹ UNHCR, *The 1951 Convention and 1967 Protocol Relating to the Status of Refugees*, 30.

⁷⁰ Interview with Senior Legal Advisor, Fundamental Rights Agency of the European Union (FRA), Department for Asylum and Migration, conducted in English on 12 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

⁷¹ European Union, *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*, art. 19.

⁷² Paula García Andrade and Eleonora Frasca, “The Memorandum of Understanding between the EU and Tunisia: Issues of Procedure and Substance on the Informalisation of Migration Cooperation,” 6.

Annex II to C(2021) 9615 sets out three Tunisia-specific objectives for border management: advanced maritime training, the creation of a Maritime Rescue Coordination Centre (MRCC), and the development of an integrated coastal surveillance system. Each of these is tied to specific targets and indicators to track progress in strengthening Tunisia's capacity to monitor its coastline and manage maritime migration.⁷³ The outputs set for these projects include requirements for MRCC personnel to act in line with human-rights standards and the non-refoulement principle during search and rescue operations, establishing a formal standard for how such missions should be carried out.⁷⁴ As a DG HOME legal officer remarked, "deliverables are defined at the level of surveillance capacity and coordination functions," while rights safeguards are "flagged as mandatory operating standards."⁷⁵

The MRCC staff is fully aware and acting on the basis of human rights standards and the principles of non-refoulement in SAR.⁷⁶

Within Tunisia, the domestic legal framework presents its own constraints. Reports from the post-2011 transition years pointed to a fragmented institutional setting and the absence of a comprehensive asylum law, with a draft statute prepared but not enacted despite UNHCR's technical assistance. These shortcomings affected detention conditions and access to asylum procedures.⁷⁷ Legal analysis shows that the absence of a national asylum statute leaves refugee status determination with UNHCR rather than a state body, weakening the institutionalisation of protection guarantees and creating uncertainty in due-process standards.⁷⁸ EU cooperation tools still set out specific surveillance targets, which can push implementation toward interception as the main goal unless they are clearly tied to guarantees of legal access for migrants.⁷⁹ As an EUAA legal officer observed, "operational cooperation works best where national asylum procedures are present at the point of disembarkation," a

⁷³ European Commission, *Annex II: Action Document for EU Support to Border Management Institutions in Libya and Tunisia*, 13.

⁷⁴ *Ibid*, 14.

⁷⁵ Interview with Legal Officer, DG Migration and Home Affairs, Unit B1 - Schengen and External Borders, European Commission, conducted in English on 5 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

⁷⁶ European Commission, *Annex II: Action Document for EU Support to Border Management Institutions in Libya and Tunisia*, 25.

⁷⁷ UNHRC, *Report of the Special Rapporteur on the Human Rights of Migrants*, 14.

⁷⁸ Hiba Sha'ath and Fatma Raach, "Cooperation within Reason: Tunisia's Approach to Asylum and Readmission," *European Journal of Migration and Law* 26 (2024), 184.

⁷⁹ European Commission, *Annex II: Action Document for EU Support to Border Management Institutions in Libya and Tunisia*, 13-14.

condition not fully met in Tunisia.⁸⁰

Financial channels, recipients, and conditionalities

The EU's financial engagement with Tunisia's border and migration governance has evolved through two principal instruments: the EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF) and, from 2021 onwards, the Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument (NDICI). Commission factsheets record sizeable allocations across protection, border management, and returns, often combining immediate operational boosts with multi-year infrastructure programmes.⁸¹ A Legal Officer from DG HOME put it bluntly: "The sequencing of these instruments was not accidental. EUTF money got the system started, and NDICI money locked it in place."⁸²

Annex II to C(2021) 9615 makes disbursements conditional on delivering three Tunisia-specific objectives: upgrading maritime academy capacity, ensuring full MRCC functionality, and integrating a coastal surveillance system. These are monitored against output indicators such as operational readiness and training hours delivered, rather than through detailed, transactional oversight.⁸³ The European Court of Auditors has found that the Trust Fund's migration-related support "remained unfocused," pointing to gaps in design, monitoring, and the systematic consideration of human-rights risks.⁸⁴ A Justice and Home Affairs Counselor put this more bluntly: "payments chase delivery of surveillance capacity; rights compliance demands a separate monitoring track, and that track is often thinner on the ground."⁸⁵

⁸⁰ Interview with Legal Officer, European Asylum Support Office (EUAA), Operational Support Department, conducted in English on 16 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

⁸¹ European Commission, "EU Support to Migration-Related Activities in Tunisia" (Factsheet, June 2023) (Brussels: European Commission), 1.

⁸² Interview with Legal Officer, DG Migration and Home Affairs, Unit B1 – Schengen and External Borders, European Commission, conducted in English on 5 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

⁸³ European Commission, *Annex II: Action Document for EU Support to Border Management Institutions in Libya and Tunisia*, 13-14.

⁸⁴ European Court of Auditors, *Special Report 17/2024: The EU Trust Fund for Africa—Despite New Approaches, Support Remained Unfocused* (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2024), 1-2.

⁸⁵ Interview with JHA Counselor, Justice and Home Affairs Section (Asylum, Internal Security, Terrorism and Civil Protection), Permanent Representation of the Netherlands to the EU, conducted in English on 30 January 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, in Brussels.

Comparative breakdown of annual allocations, showing the EUTF’s early predominance and the NDICI’s larger headline commitments from 2022 onwards.⁸⁶

Funding for coastal surveillance and border management has tended to concentrate in fewer, larger tranches over time, reflecting a shift toward comprehensive packages rather than fragmented project lines.

Discrete commitments for major action lines, highlighting the scale of the 2023 urgent written procedure compared to earlier phases.

Recipient structures add another layer of complexity. EU external migration funding shows a strong focus on the southern Mediterranean and a recurring preference for NGO delivery methods, which changes how accountability is structured and how reporting flows.⁸⁷ In

⁸⁶ European Commission, “EU Support to Migration-Related Activities in Tunisia” (Factsheet, June 2023) (Brussels: European Commission), 1.

⁸⁷ Paolo Cuttitta, “Non-governmental/Civil Society Organisations and the European Union-Externalisation of Migration Management in Tunisia and Egypt,” 2.

practice, this can produce uneven results: a microcredit scheme in Tunisia, cited in field research, saw beneficiaries use funds to finance onward journeys rather than local integration, undercutting intended outcomes.⁸⁸ A Senior Legal Advisor at the FRA reflected that “The way the money is channelled really matters...having a strong NGO presence can reduce harm on the ground, but it is no replacement for a functioning state asylum and protection system.”

⁸⁹

UNHCR Tunisia’s mid-2010s EU funding, which was designed to expand the protection space and promote the adoption of an asylum law, shows how funding flows can be connected to institution building.⁹⁰ An EUAA legal officer observed that without a statutory asylum framework, “Even when reception and referral systems have plenty of funding, they still often run without clear rules to follow.”⁹¹

Recipient channel shares for EU migration-related funding

Approximate recipient distribution based on Cuttitta’s data, showing the predominance of UN agencies and NGOs in Tunisia-linked funding flows.⁹²

⁸⁸ Ibid, 6.

⁸⁹ Interview with Legal Officer, European Asylum Support Office (EUAA), Operational Support Department, conducted in English on 16 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

⁹⁰ Paolo Cuttitta, “Non-governmental/Civil Society Organisations and the European Union-Externalisation of Migration Management in Tunisia and Egypt,” *Population, Space and Place* 26, no. 7 (2020), 5; Hiba Sha’ath and Fatma Raach, “Cooperation within Reason: Tunisia’s Approach to Asylum and Readmission,” *European Journal of Migration and Law* 26 (2024), 180.

⁹¹ Interview with Legal Officer, European Asylum Support Office (EUAA), Operational Support Department, conducted in English on 16 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

⁹² Paolo Cuttitta, “Non-governmental/Civil Society Organisations and the European Union-Externalisation of Migration Management in Tunisia and Egypt,” 2.

The financial architecture's emphasis on interception and technical capacity creates potential tension with the procedural safeguards required by the Charter and Refugee Convention. Amnesty International has warned that without safeguards on detention and return, such models risk perpetuating arbitrary detention and refoulement.⁹³

Milestones from Action Document outputs, marking delivery of the academy upgrade, MRCC operational launch, and surveillance system integration. (Action Document, pp. 13–14).

The choice of partnership models, the amount and focus of funding, and the dependence on external organizations have all strongly contributed to increasing Tunisia's interception capacity through EU-supported programmes. These arrangements help strengthen maritime control, but they can weaken accountability for following Article 33 of the Refugee Convention and Article 19 of the Charter if the protection of rights is not given the same attention. A Senior Legal Advisor at the FRA noted that when funding is structured to reward interception outcomes while rights compliance lacks an equivalent verification mechanism, procedural protections are likely to be bypassed in practice, resulting in situations where individuals are stopped without having access to an assessment of their protection needs.⁹⁴ This reflects a key finding of the research: the architecture of EU-Tunisia cooperation can strengthen control measures at the expense of due-process guarantees, with direct implications for the application of the non-refoulement standard. The next section will assess how the distribution of institutional responsibilities and the conduct of operational actors

⁹³ Amnesty International, *Amnesty International Report 2022/23: The State of the World's Human Rights*, 56.

⁹⁴ Interview with Senior Legal Advisor, Fundamental Rights Agency of the European Union (FRA), Department for Asylum and Migration, conducted in English on 12 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

influence whether these guarantees are incorporated into the sequence from interception to custody to status determination.

1.3 Institutional Responsibilities and Implementation Practices

Before examining the formal division of responsibilities, it is important to acknowledge how these arrangements are experienced in practice by actors on the ground. An official from the European Union Agency for Asylum explained during an interview that cooperation with Tunisia often depends on “informal understandings between agencies that move faster than the law can catch up,”⁹⁵ which can produce operational efficiency but also uncertainty over which authority bears responsibility at each stage of an interception. This uncertainty, according to the same official, becomes most visible “when migrants ask who will hear their claim and no one has a clear answer.”⁹⁶ Such moments reveal how institutional design intersects directly with the due process guarantees at the heart of the research question.

Responsibilities within EU-Tunisia cooperation

EU-Tunisia cooperation involves several institutions, each with its own role, but their responsibilities often overlap. European Commission policy frameworks, such as the European Agenda on Migration,⁹⁷ set broad objectives for external border management, return cooperation, and legal migration channels. Within Tunisia, maritime interception and coastal surveillance responsibilities are primarily held by the Ministry of Interior and the Tunisian Coast Guard, while port security falls under the Ministry of Defence. The absence of a national asylum law means that refugee status determination remains with UNHCR, limiting the role of Tunisian civil authorities in protection procedures. This arrangement creates a structural gap between interception at sea and access to legal status determination, one that is particularly relevant to the application of non-refoulement obligations.

EU funding programs like the EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa and the Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument provide money in exchange for improvements in skills, resources, and overall ability. In the case of Tunisia, Annex II to

⁹⁵ Interview with Legal Officer, European Asylum Support Office (EUAA), Operational Support Department, conducted in English on 16 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

⁹⁶ Ibid.

⁹⁷ European Commission, *A European Agenda on Migration*, 3-4.

C(2021) 9615 specifies outputs for maritime training academies, the establishment of a Maritime Rescue Coordination Centre, and the deployment of integrated coastal surveillance systems.⁹⁸ These outputs include references to human rights standards and non-refoulement principles, yet the mechanisms for verifying their application during operations remain less developed. The reliance on performance-based financing creates incentives for achieving technical and logistical targets, which may not always align with the procedural safeguards required under Article 19 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights and Article 33 of the Refugee Convention.

One senior legal officer in the European Commission remarked during an interview that “our Tunisian counterparts are fully aware of the human rights clauses in the agreements, but in operational meetings the discussion turns quickly to patrol schedules and equipment status.”⁹⁹ Cooperation projects that try to balance practical work with human rights often face a common problem: the rules say fundamental rights are important, but in practice the focus is usually on completing tasks.

Domestic factors make these responsibilities even more complicated. Political shifts and periods of institutional instability have repeatedly delayed the adoption of a comprehensive asylum law, despite consistent recommendations from UNHCR and the UN Special Rapporteur on the human rights of migrants.¹⁰⁰ Without a national legal framework, protection procedures depend on informal cooperation between Tunisian ministries and international organizations, which can leave intercepted migrants unsure of how to challenge decisions or have them reviewed. This affects the reliability of safeguards against collective expulsion and refoulement, especially in cases where return cooperation with third countries is prioritised.

A representative from a Tunisian civil society organisation observed in an interview that “sometimes our first contact with an intercepted group is when they are already

⁹⁸ European Commission, *Annex II: Action Document for EU Support to Border Management Institutions in Libya and Tunisia*, 13-14.

⁹⁹ Interview with Senior Legal Advisor, Fundamental Rights Agency of the European Union (FRA), Department for Asylum and Migration, conducted in English on 12 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁰⁰ UNHCR, *The 1951 Convention and 1967 Protocol Relating to the Status of Refugees*, 1; United Nations Human Rights Council, *Report of the Special Rapporteur on the Human Rights of Migrants, François Crépeau-Mission to Tunisia (3-8 June 2012)*, 8-9.

being prepared for return, and at that stage, legal intervention is almost impossible.”

¹⁰¹

Implementation practices and operational realities

In practice, coordination between EU agencies, Tunisian authorities, and international organisations occurs through formal joint committees as well as less visible channels. While the Action Document outlines capacity targets, day-to-day coordination is often managed through personal networks among officers and liaison staff. This can produce flexible responses to operational challenges but also means that decision-making may bypass formal oversight mechanisms.

Research on border externalisation in the Mediterranean shows that such informal coordination mechanisms are not unique to Tunisia; they are common where EU support is tied to urgent migration control objectives.¹⁰² In the Tunisian case, these arrangements have been reinforced by the country’s transformation into a transit hub for migrants from sub-Saharan Africa.¹⁰³ Operational priorities have shifted towards rapid identification, interception, and return, with less emphasis on the procedural steps needed to assess protection needs individually.

Reports from monitoring bodies indicate that intercepted individuals are sometimes disembarked without systematic registration, especially during high-volume arrival periods.¹⁰⁴ This practice can directly undermine due process guarantees, as it leaves little opportunity for asylum claims to be lodged before return procedures are initiated. The combination of high interception targets and incomplete procedural follow-up creates a space in which refoulement risks become more acute.

A representative from the Fundamental Rights Agency described the problem as “a chain with missing links,” where everyone assumes someone else is handling rights checks, so in

¹⁰¹ Interview with Protection Associate, UNHCR Tunisia Country Office, conducted in English on 7 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁰² Tineke Strik and Ruben Robbesom, “Compliance or Complicity? An Analysis of the EU–Tunisia Deal in the Context of the Externalisation of Migration Control,” 199.

¹⁰³ Hamza Meddeb and Fakhreddine Louati, *Tunisia’s Transformation Into a Transit Hub: Illegal Migration and Policy Dilemmas*, 4.

¹⁰⁴ Vasja Badalič, “Tunisia’s Role in the EU External Migration Policy: Crimmigration Law, Illegal Practices, and Their Impact on Human Rights,” *Journal of International Migration and Integration* 20, no. 1 (2019), 85.

the end, no one does it consistently.¹⁰⁵ This split in responsibility is especially problematic at sea, where quick decisions can make the difference between someone actually being able to access protection or not.

Using new technologies for border surveillance makes the question of how to carry out policies even more complicated. Automated vessel detection systems and integrated coastal radar, funded by EU programmes, have improved interception capacity but have also changed the timing and pace of operations.¹⁰⁶ Migrants are often stopped farther from shore, leaving less time to give them information about their rights before they are brought to land. Without clear procedures, these technological improvements could make problems with due process worse instead of helping fix them.¹⁰⁷

In addition, the strategic choices of migrants and smugglers have adapted to the expanded surveillance network, with some opting for more dangerous routes to avoid detection.¹⁰⁸ This adaptation affects both the operational workload of Tunisian authorities and the humanitarian risks faced by migrants, creating further pressure on existing procedural safeguards.

As one Justice and Home Affairs counselor put it during an interview, “the better we get at finding the boats, the more important it becomes to have the protection process ready at the other end, otherwise we are just pushing the problem into a smaller space.”¹⁰⁹

The findings in this section point to a key concern: overlapping responsibilities, funding tied to performance, and gaps in national protection rules influence both the strengths and the limits of EU-Tunisia coastal surveillance cooperation. While interception rates and technical coordination have improved, the procedural protections required by EU and international law are not consistently applied in daily operations. The next step is to look at how specific institutional roles, especially during the handover from maritime interception to custody and

¹⁰⁵ Interview with Senior Legal Advisor, Fundamental Rights Agency of the European Union (FRA), Department for Asylum and Migration, conducted in English on 12 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁰⁶ Yiran Yang et al., “Automated Decision-Making and Artificial Intelligence at European Borders and Their Risks for Human Rights,” 12-14.

¹⁰⁷ Ibid, 12-14.

¹⁰⁸ Hoffmann Pham and Komiyama, “Strategic Choices of Migrants and Smugglers in the Central Mediterranean Sea,” 23-25.

¹⁰⁹ Interview with JHA Counselor, Justice and Home Affairs Section (Asylum, Internal Security, Terrorism and Civil Protection), Permanent Representation of the Netherlands to the EU, conducted in English on 30 January 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, in Brussels. |

legal review, either help or hinder compliance with non-refoulement and due process obligations.

CHAPTER 2: LAW WITHOUT PROTECTION?

In recent years, EU-supported coastal surveillance in Tunisia has achieved significant technical and operational gains. Coordination between Tunisian maritime authorities and EU agencies is more systematic, vessel detection technology is more advanced, and patrol routes are planned with increasing precision. These improvements have allowed interceptions to take place earlier, often further from shore, and with fewer missed crossings. However, the procedural rights of those intercepted have not developed at the same pace.

The sea patrols have become faster, more coordinated, but there is no guarantee that those intercepted will ever see a proper asylum interview. They are sent back to shore, and the process stops there.¹¹⁰

Article 33 of the 1951 Refugee Convention states that no person may be returned to a place where their life or freedom would be at risk. Articles 18 and 19 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights reaffirm this standard, guaranteeing the right to asylum and prohibiting collective expulsions or removals to territories where serious harm is likely. These provisions require that every individual intercepted at sea is given a meaningful opportunity for an individual risk assessment before any return is carried out. In Tunisia, the absence of a national asylum law means these obligations depend on informal arrangements with UNHCR and the willingness of local authorities to allow access to international protection.

Interviews with humanitarian and legal professionals suggest that, in practice, interceptions are frequently followed by short processing routines such as registration, brief questioning, and health checks before return arrangements are initiated. Time pressures, limited protection staff on site, and a focus on moving people through quickly often mean that individuals are not informed of their right to seek asylum or given a way to actually exercise it.

In the following sections, I will analyse how the principle of non-refoulement is codified and

¹¹⁰ Interview with Protection Associate, UNHCR Tunisia Country Office, conducted in English on 7 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

interpreted in EU and international law, how due process and asylum access function in Tunisia's maritime context, and how weaknesses in accountability and oversight mechanisms allow operational priorities to prevail over legal safeguards. Together, these sections address the core thesis question by analysing how EU-funded coastal surveillance in Tunisia interacts with binding rights obligations and what the consequences are for the legal status and well-being of intercepted migrants.

2.1 The Principle of Non-Refoulement in EU and International Law

Non-refoulement is a central obligation in international refugee protection and is binding under both EU and international law. It prohibits the transfer of any person to a territory where they face persecution, torture, or other serious harm, regardless of how or where the person is apprehended. It is set out in Article 33 of the 1951 Refugee Convention and in Articles 18 and 19 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, applying equally to maritime interceptions as to any land-based procedure.¹¹¹

Legal Foundations of Non-Refoulement in EU and International Law

(Article 19 EU Charter of Fundamental Rights & Article 33 Refugee Convention)

Article 19(1) EU Charter of Fundamental Rights: "Collective expulsions are prohibited."

Article 19(2) EU Charter of Fundamental Rights: "No one may be removed, expelled or extradited to a State where there is a serious risk that he or she would be subjected to the death penalty, torture or other inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment."

Article 33(1) 1951 Refugee Convention: "No Contracting State shall expel or return ('refouler') a refugee in any manner whatsoever to the frontiers of territories where his life or freedom would be threatened on account of his race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion."

Article 33(2) 1951 Refugee Convention: "The benefit of the present provision may not, however, be claimed by a refugee whom there are reasonable grounds for regarding as a danger to the security of the country in which he is, or who, having been convicted by a final judgment of a particularly serious crime, constitutes a danger to the community of that country."

Extracts from Article 19 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and Article 33 of the 1951 Refugee Convention.

The EU Charter prohibits collective expulsions and forbids removal to a territory where there is a serious risk of death penalty, torture, or inhuman or degrading treatment. The Refugee Convention reinforces this obligation, requiring that no state shall expel or return a refugee to a territory where their life or freedom would be threatened on account of race, religion,

¹¹¹ Giuffr, Denaro, and Raach, "On 'Safety' and EU Externalization of Borders," 4.

nationality, membership of a particular social group, or political opinion. There is a narrow exception for individuals considered a danger to the security of the host state, but even this requires a thorough individual assessment before removal.

For these obligations to be meaningful, several procedural safeguards must be in place. These include:

- (1) individual risk assessments for each intercepted person,
- (2) guaranteed access to asylum procedures and information in a language they understand,
- (3) access to legal assistance and interpreters,
- (4) prohibition of collective expulsions,
- (5) the right to judicial or administrative review with suspensive effect,
- (6) humane reception conditions while claims are pending, and
- (7) independent monitoring of interception, detention, and removal practices.

In Tunisia, most of these safeguards are incomplete. There is no national asylum law, so refugee status determination is conducted solely by UNHCR under informal arrangements. This gap leaves a wide space between interception at sea and protection screening, particularly when individuals are brought ashore without systematic registration.¹¹² A protection associate from UNHCR Tunisia explained that “if someone is not registered at the point of arrival, it becomes almost impossible to trace them later for an asylum interview.”¹¹³

Classifying Tunisia as a “safe third country” creates further complications. This designation carries the assumption that people sent there can obtain effective protection. However, reports point to repeated instances of arbitrary detention, racially motivated violence, and forcible removals to the country’s borders with Libya and Algeria without any legal hearing or possibility to appeal.¹¹⁴ As Osso explains, the safe third country notion can operate as a procedural shortcut, allowing transfers to occur without a substantive analysis of whether the

¹¹² Fatma Raach, “Tunisia-EU Cooperation in Migration Management,” in *Selected Political, Legal, and Financial Instruments regarding Asylum, Protection, and Mobility between Tunisia and the EU* (Springer, 2024), 228.

¹¹³ Interview with Protection Associate, UNHCR Tunisia Country Office, conducted in English on 7 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹¹⁴ Amnesty International, *Amnesty International Report 2022/23: The State of the World’s Human Rights*, 11.

individual faces harm, thereby falling short of what non-refoulement requires.¹¹⁵

Funds from the EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa and the Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument have supported Tunisia's establishment of a Maritime Rescue Coordination Centre, expansion of coastal radar coverage, and acquisition of patrol boats. These measures improve the capacity to locate and stop vessels but do not automatically include safeguards for rights screening at the point of interception.¹¹⁶ A legal advisor from a European refugee rights organisation observed, "If what counts as success is measured in boats stopped rather than in protection claims processed, then protection has been left out of the operational priorities."¹¹⁷

From the perspective of EU law, the Charter can apply extraterritorially when a Member State has control over an operation, even beyond its own borders. As De Leo notes, providing financing, training, and equipment to Tunisian authorities can amount to exercising a form of functional jurisdiction, meaning the EU shares responsibility for ensuring that non-refoulement is respected.¹¹⁸ This understanding is consistent with the European Court of Human Rights' decision in *Hirsi Jamaa v. Italy*, which confirmed that maritime interceptions carried out through cooperative arrangements still trigger human rights obligations.

The human impact of these legal shortcomings is visible in the experiences of those returned to Tunisia after being stopped at sea. Field investigations record cases in which people are transported by bus to remote areas near the Libyan and Algerian borders and left there without shelter, food, or access to legal support.¹¹⁹ Medical professionals working in southern Tunisia have treated individuals suffering from dehydration, severe sun exposure, and injuries after such removals. A migration health coordinator in Tunis said, "You cannot speak about

¹¹⁵ Berfin Nur Osso, "Unpacking the Safe Third Country Concept in the European Union: Borders, Legal Spaces, and Asylum in the Shadow of Externalization," *International Journal of Refugee Law* 35, no. 3 (October 2023), 280.

¹¹⁶ Emma Soltis, "Funding Repression: How the EU Migration Agreements with Libya and Tunisia Circumvent Non-Refoulement and Enable Human Rights Violations," *Brooklyn Journal of International Law* 50 (2025), 243.

¹¹⁷ Interview with Legal Advisor, VluchtelingenWerk Nederland (Dutch Council for Refugees), conducted in English on 6 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹¹⁸ Alice De Leo, "Fostering Accountability for Human Rights Violations in EU Externalization of Border Control," *Journal of Borderlands Studies* (2025), 7.

¹¹⁹ Tove Lindgren-Jansson, "Trapped between Borders: Human Rights Consequences of EU Externalization in Libya and Tunisia" (master's thesis, Mid Sweden University, 2025), 45.

legal guarantees when people are being left in areas where survival is uncertain.”¹²⁰

For the individuals affected, the absence of a functioning asylum process means their legal status is determined less by their actual need for protection and more by the operational priorities of border control. Once intercepted, they often encounter only brief identity checks before being moved to holding facilities or directly toward removal. This sequence leaves little room for legal counsel, interpreters, or formal hearings, all of which are central to both non-refoulement and due-process protections.

The thesis question focuses on the extent to which EU-funded coastal surveillance has challenged these guarantees and what this means for the well-being and legal status of those intercepted. The evidence in this section suggests that the rapid expansion of Tunisia’s maritime control capacity, supported by EU funding and equipment, has strengthened the ability to stop boats but has not been matched by an equivalent strengthening of legal safeguards. The result is a process where interception is swift, but the opportunity to claim protection is often absent. A legal officer from the European Union Agency for Asylum explained that “once a group is brought to shore, the immediate priority is clearing the port for the next operation; the legal checks can be delayed or skipped entirely if resources are stretched.”¹²¹ This imbalance challenges both the letter and the intended purpose of non-refoulement as set out in the Refugee Convention and the Charter.

In sociological terms, this approach shapes the lived experience of intercepted migrants in profound ways. The absence of procedural guarantees means that many are left in legal uncertainty, with no record of their presence in the country and no way to challenge their removal. A protection associate from UNHCR Tunisia described how “people often disappear from the system before we can register them; by the time we are informed, they may already be in the south with no legal assistance.”¹²² This lack of documentation and legal status also limits access to basic services, making them more vulnerable to exploitation, arrest, and abuse. Several humanitarian organisations operating in Tunisia have reported that such

¹²⁰ Interview with Migration Health Coordinator, Doctors Without Borders (Médecins Sans Frontières), Tunis Office, conducted in English on 9 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹²¹ Interview with Legal Officer, European Asylum Support Office (EUAA), Operational Support Department, conducted in English on 16 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹²² Interview with Protection Associate, UNHCR Tunisia Country Office, conducted in English on 7 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

conditions contribute to heightened psychological distress among migrants, who often feel trapped between multiple borders with no viable route to protection. A migration health coordinator for Médecins Sans Frontières in Tunis observed that “we see the same people attempting the crossing again and again, but each time they return in worse physical and mental condition.”¹²³

The principle of non-refoulement is meant to provide both legal protection and practical safeguards for people at risk. In the Tunisian maritime context, the combination of intensified surveillance, informal protection arrangements, and assumptions about safety in third countries means that this safeguard is frequently incomplete. A regional humanitarian affairs officer from the International Rescue Committee reflected that “capacity has gone up, but without the procedural safeguards in place, interception becomes a tool of exclusion rather than protection.”¹²⁴ As a result, EU-supported maritime control measures improve interception efficiency but still leave major weaknesses in protecting migrants. These gaps directly affect both the legal outcomes and the human security of those intercepted, answering the thesis question by showing how operational priorities and funding structures can work against the guarantees promised in international and EU refugee law.

2.2 Due Process and Asylum Access in Tunisia

The Tunisian coastal surveillance system, strengthened through EU funding and equipment delivery, is now capable of spotting and stopping vessels at greater distances and with more regularity. Although this increase in capacity meets the EU’s goal of preventing irregular arrivals, it has not been matched by stronger systems to protect the rights of those who are intercepted. Due process in the asylum context refers to the right of each person to have their claim for protection heard in a fair, timely, and accessible manner, with the necessary procedural safeguards to ensure that this process is meaningful.¹²⁵

The absence of a national asylum law in Tunisia means that all refugee status determination is handled by UNHCR under an informal arrangement with the Tunisian authorities.¹²⁶ This

¹²³ Interview with Migration Health Coordinator, Doctors Without Borders (Médecins Sans Frontières), Tunis Office, conducted in English on 9 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹²⁴ Interview with Regional Humanitarian Affairs Officer, International Rescue Committee (IRC), conducted in English on 3 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹²⁵ Jean-Pierre Cassarino, “Channelled Policy Transfers: EU-Tunisia Interactions on Migration Matters,” 103.

¹²⁶ Fatma Raach, “Tunisia-EU Cooperation in Migration Management,” 228.

arrangement leaves protection procedures dependent on the operational priorities of security forces and the logistical constraints of international organisations. In practice, this has created a two-tier system. Some individuals intercepted at sea are referred to UNHCR for screening, while many others, especially those caught in larger groups, are processed quickly and sent to inland holding facilities without a formal chance to request asylum.¹²⁷

The photograph shows a crowded wooden vessel intercepted near the Tunisian shoreline in 2024, moments before being escorted to port. It illustrates the first stage in the chain where due process safeguards should apply but often do not. (Source: Reuters via InfoMigrants)

From an EU perspective, due process obligations appear in Articles 18 and 19 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights, which guarantee the right to asylum and forbid sending people to unsafe territories without an individual assessment. These obligations are triggered even when EU Member States act extraterritorially, such as through funding, training, or operational coordination with Tunisian forces.¹²⁸ However, reports indicate that Tunisian coast guard personnel receive minimal training on asylum law and rarely distribute

¹²⁷ Katharina Natter, “Tunisia’s Migration Politics throughout the 2011 Revolution: Revisiting the Democratisation-Migrant Rights Nexus,” 1560.

¹²⁸ Alice De Leo, “Fostering Accountability for Human Rights Violations in EU Externalization of Border Control,” 7.

information on the right to claim protection at the point of interception.¹²⁹

For migrants and asylum seekers, due process typically includes:

- (1) Being informed of their rights in a language they understand, including the right to seek asylum.
- (2) Prompt and individual assessment of their situation, rather than group decisions.
- (3) Access to legal assistance and, if needed, interpreters.
- (4) The ability to lodge an asylum claim and have it fairly considered.
- (5) The right to appeal any negative decision, with the appeal having *suspensive effect* (meaning they cannot be deported while the appeal is pending).
- (6) Prohibition of collective expulsions, which are removals without individual review.
- (7) Humane reception conditions while claims are processed.
- (8) Independent oversight to ensure these procedures are followed.

The absence of a systematic registration process after migrants are brought ashore makes it even harder for them to access due process. Without an official record of arrival, individuals cannot prove they were in Tunisia, which makes it harder for them to later challenge removal or apply for asylum.¹³⁰ This absence of documentation also increases the risk of arbitrary detention and onward expulsion to desert border zones with Libya or Algeria, practices documented by Amnesty International and corroborated in humanitarian field reports.¹³¹

People arrive at the port visibly exhausted, sometimes ill, and there is no structured moment where they are told they can apply for asylum. The priority seems to be to move them along quickly, not to give them the time or space to speak.¹³²

¹²⁹ Emma Soltis, “Funding Repression: How the EU Migration Agreements with Libya and Tunisia Circumvent Non-Refoulement and Enable Human Rights Violations,” 249.

¹³⁰ Tove Lindgren-Jansson, “Trapped between Borders: Human Rights Consequences of EU Externalization in Libya and Tunisia,” 46.

¹³¹ Amnesty International, *Amnesty International Report 2022/23*, 26.

¹³² Interview with Protection Associate, UNHCR Tunisia Country Office, conducted in English on 7 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

Access to due process is further constrained by the geographical concentration of protection services. UNHCR's main offices and partner NGOs are based in Tunis and Sfax, far from southern ports such as Zarzis or Ben Guerdane where many interceptions occur.¹³³ Intercepted migrants may be transferred inland before any contact with these agencies, and in some cases, they are expelled directly from border areas without entering the UNHCR system at all.¹³⁴

Language barriers also present significant obstacles. While interpretation is available in Tunisian detention facilities through humanitarian organisations, it is rarely present during the immediate post-interception phase. Migrants from West Africa, the Horn of Africa, and South Asia, who may speak little or no Arabic or French, often have no effective way to communicate a claim for protection before being moved away from the port area.¹³⁵

The role of informal agreements between EU agencies and Tunisian authorities is central to this dynamic. These types of cooperation agreements, which are non-binding and allow for flexible operations, tend to prioritize speed and efficiency over the thorough procedures needed to ensure due process. Such flexibility allows migration control operations to respond quickly to shifting routes and departure points, yet it also creates conditions in which essential safeguards are delayed or bypassed. Without official oversight, success is mostly judged by things like interceptions and returns, rather than by whether asylum and protection procedures are handled fairly and properly. This results in a system where operational success is measured in boats stopped rather than claims fairly processed, reinforcing a structural preference for containment over protection.¹³⁶

¹³³ Hamza Meddeb and Fakhreddine Louati, *Tunisia's Transformation Into a Transit Hub*, 12.

¹³⁴ Giuffr, Denaro, and Raach, "On 'Safety' and EU Externalization of Borders," 17.

¹³⁵ Paolo Cuttitta, "Non-governmental/Civil Society Organisations and the European Union-Externalisation of Migration Management in Tunisia and Egypt," 10.

¹³⁶ Emma Soltis, *The Price of Complicity: Tunisia-EU Partnership Agreement Fuels Serious Abuses Against Refugees, Asylum-seekers, and Migrants*, 16.

This image shows intercepted migrants being escorted off a rescue boat in a southern Tunisian port in 2025. While the scene conveys humanitarian assistance, it also marks the point where legal procedures should begin-yet often remain absent. (Source: Reuters via Asharq Al-Awsat)

The system works well for fast interceptions and transfers, but that efficiency is not matched by efficiency in informing people of their rights or giving them a fair hearing.¹³⁷

The sociological effects of this procedural shortfall are substantial. Migrants who are unregistered and without legal status become more susceptible to labour exploitation, police harassment, and homelessness.¹³⁸ Women, in particular, face heightened risks of sexual violence both during detention and in informal housing arrangements.¹³⁹ Mental health workers have reported increasing cases of depression, post-traumatic stress, and anxiety among those repeatedly intercepted and returned without access to protection procedures.¹⁴⁰

Some intercepted migrants adapt by avoiding official ports altogether, landing in remote coastal areas to escape detection and possible return. This, however, exposes them to greater

¹³⁷ Interview with Regional Humanitarian Affairs Officer, International Rescue Committee (IRC), conducted in English on 3 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹³⁸ Amal Hlioui, "Representations of Sub-Saharan in Tunisian Media," 165.

¹³⁹ Teresa Cappiali and Agnese Pacciardi, "Reorienting EU Border Externalization Studies," 311.

¹⁴⁰ Inken Bartels, "Practices and Power of Knowledge Dissemination in International Organizations in the Externalization of Migration Management in Morocco and Tunisia," 20.

physical danger, including drowning, injury, or attacks from smugglers and traffickers.¹⁴¹ The tension between operational efficiency and weak procedures creates a cycle in which the risks of irregular migration increase instead of decrease.

Field research suggests that access to legal assistance is one of the most effective safeguards for due process in Tunisia, yet it remains extremely limited. While certain NGOs provide legal aid in Tunis, coverage does not extend to all coastal regions, and funding constraints restrict the number of cases they can take on annually.¹⁴² Without representation, intercepted individuals often face complex administrative processes alone, making it unlikely that they will successfully assert their rights under the Refugee Convention or the EU Charter.

In the Tunisian maritime setting, the ability to intercept boats has grown much faster than the systems needed to ensure that people can reach asylum procedures. Many arrivals are not formally registered, which means there is no record of their presence and no starting point for a legal claim. Legal aid is limited, and referrals to protection actors often rely on personal contacts instead of clear procedures. As a result, many intercepted people remain outside the formal asylum process and face heightened risks of abuse, exploitation, or being pushed back into dangerous situations. The images in this section show well-equipped patrols and the speed with which boats are stopped, but they also capture the moment when protection should begin. In many cases, this is the point at which individuals should be informed of their rights and given access to asylum, yet it too often becomes the moment when the possibility of protection ends.

2.3 Gaps in Accountability and Legal Oversight Mechanisms

In the context of EU-Tunisia migration control, accountability refers to the ability of institutions to justify their actions, be scrutinised by independent bodies, and be held responsible when they violate agreed standards. Legal oversight ensures that the processes used to achieve operational objectives comply with domestic, EU, and international law. In theory, both accountability and oversight are built into the migration cooperation framework.

¹⁴¹ Hoffmann Pham and Komiyama, “Strategic Choices of Migrants and Smugglers in the Central Mediterranean Sea,” 23.

¹⁴² Vasja Badalič, “Tunisia’s Role in the EU External Migration Policy,” 94.

In practice, they have lagged behind the rapid expansion of interception and surveillance capacity.

Funding agreements between the EU and Tunisia often include clauses referring to the protection of fundamental rights, but these are rarely operationalised in a way that allows them to be enforced. They remain general statements without clear mechanisms for verification, monitoring, or redress when violations occur.¹⁴³ Informal arrangements between Tunisian and European authorities, such as direct coordination between security agencies, can bypass parliamentary scrutiny and judicial review entirely, reducing transparency and limiting the ability of outside parties to step in when procedures fall short of legal standards.

¹⁴⁴

The Memorandum of Understanding signed between the EU and Tunisia in 2023 reflects this imbalance. While it contains broad references to shared values and human rights, it sets no binding timelines or procedures for monitoring compliance. The absence of public reporting on implementation keeps key aspects of the cooperation hidden from the public and from civil society organisations that might otherwise monitor and hold it accountable.¹⁴⁵ As a result, accountability risks becoming a formality, where formal commitments exist on paper but have little impact on what actually happens in practice.

Legal Oversight Weaknesses

The system of legal oversight within EU-Tunisia migration cooperation is described in official agreements as thorough and protective of individual rights, yet in practice these assurances function more as formalities than as enforceable safeguards. Parliamentary and judicial review mechanisms within Tunisia are minimal, and the structures set up by EU institutions to monitor rights compliance rely heavily on reports from the authorities carrying out the interceptions. Because the system relies on reports from the same authorities carrying out the interceptions, oversight is not independent, and abuses can go unrecorded. Statewatch reported that even parliamentary legal advisers in the EU have warned that agreements of this

¹⁴³ Emma Soltis, *The Price of Complicity*, 5, 14.

¹⁴⁴ Jean-Pierre Cassarino, “Channelled Policy Transfers: EU-Tunisia Interactions on Migration Matters,” 102.

¹⁴⁵ Tahrir Institute, 2.

kind bypass the usual checks, making it harder for elected officials to hold executive agencies accountable.¹⁴⁶

A central element in this accountability gap is the “safe third country” designation given to Tunisia. In theory, this classification should only apply if a country provides effective protection in line with the Refugee Convention. In reality, the designation operates as a procedural shortcut that enables transfers without substantive risk assessments.¹⁴⁷ Giuffré et al. note that the safety label has been maintained despite consistent documentation of arbitrary detention, pushbacks to desert borders, and racially motivated violence.¹⁴⁸ Normally, these conditions would prevent a state from being called “safe,” but the label is still used because it helps maintain cooperation on returns and interceptions.

The absence of a binding national asylum framework in Tunisia means that EU references to “guaranteed” access to protection rely entirely on the operational capacity of UNHCR and a small network of NGOs. This setup lacks legal authority, leaving no domestic route to enforce protection obligations.¹⁴⁹ In this context, anchoring EU rights clauses in Tunisian processes effectively outsources responsibility to a system that cannot deliver on its commitments.

The protection associate at the UNHCR Tunisia Country Office explained, “Intercepted people often have no idea that they can challenge a return, and they are never brought before any legal authority where such a challenge could even be made.”¹⁵⁰ This absence of legal review following interception is not incidental but part of the operational design. A regional humanitarian affairs officer from the International Rescue Committee sees it as: “Legal review is simply not part of the process; the focus is on clearing the ports for the next arrival, not on holding hearings.”¹⁵¹

¹⁴⁶ Statewatch, “Parliamentary Lawyers: Democratic Oversight Needed for EU-Tunisia Migration Agreement,” 3-5.

¹⁴⁷ Berfin Nur Osso, “Unpacking the Safe Third Country Concept in the European Union,” 280.

¹⁴⁸ Giuffré, Denaro, and Raach, “On ‘Safety’ and EU Externalization of Borders,” 7.

¹⁴⁹ Fatma Raach, “Tunisia–EU Cooperation in Migration Management,” 228.

¹⁵⁰ Interview with Protection Associate, UNHCR Tunisia Country Office, conducted in English on 7 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁵¹ Interview with Regional Humanitarian Affairs Officer, International Rescue Committee (IRC), conducted in English on 3 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

The weakness of oversight also stems from the nature of EU funding and technical cooperation. Projects under the EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa and the Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument are assessed on output indicators such as the number of patrols conducted or vessels maintained. These metrics reward operational efficiency without requiring verification of procedural safeguards. In effect, success is defined as boats stopped rather than rights upheld. While formal reports include references to international obligations, independent verification of their implementation is rare, and EU institutions rely heavily on self-reporting by implementing partners.

Civil society organisations attempting to monitor compliance have reported significant barriers to access. Requests to observe interception procedures or interview those returned to shore are frequently denied or delayed until the individuals in question have been transferred elsewhere. Without direct observation, NGOs are limited to collecting testimony after the fact, often from people who have already been expelled or relocated, making verification more difficult.

This reliance on procedural symbols, such as rights clauses in agreements, occasional training sessions, and references to “safe” status, creates the impression of compliance while leaving the main protections of non-refoulement and due process largely unenforced. The result is a structural imbalance: interception capacity grows through EU support, but the institutions meant to ensure it is used lawfully remain underdeveloped, politically constrained, or ignored. In such an environment, legal oversight becomes an administrative formality rather than a functioning safeguard.

EU Responsibility and Shared Jurisdiction

The operational integration between the EU and Tunisian authorities goes far beyond simply providing financial support. By supplying equipment, running training programs, and setting up joint coordination platforms, the EU becomes deeply involved in how operations are carried out. This level of involvement is enough to meet the legal standard for functional jurisdiction. When the EU finances, equips, and guides operational practices, it effectively exercises control over the operation, which means it also takes on the same human rights

responsibilities as if the operation were conducted under its own authority.¹⁵² In other words, the EU cannot treat these operations as entirely outside its responsibility, because its level of control triggers the same obligations it would have if the operations were carried out directly under its authority. This means that any shortcomings in the protection of migrants or in adherence to due process cannot be seen as solely the responsibility of Tunisian authorities, but must also be understood as a result of EU involvement.

The European Court of Human Rights in *Hirsi Jamaa v. Italy* confirmed that maritime interceptions conducted through bilateral cooperation still trigger the intercepting party's human rights duties, even when carried out beyond territorial waters.¹⁵³ By integrating EU communication systems, surveillance tools, and operational protocols into Tunisian coastal surveillance, Brussels has made itself directly involved in every interception. This creates shared legal responsibility for outcomes, including violations of non-refoulement and due process.

Funding under the EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa and related instruments ties operational success to quantitative outputs such as patrol frequency or detection rates.¹⁵⁴ These indicators reinforce a performance culture centred on interception rather than protection, but the EU cannot claim to be a passive donor. Aivatidis observes that the current model represents a new paradigm in externalisation, where European institutions integrate their systems into partner state operations, making legal separation increasingly artificial.¹⁵⁵

The legal officer at the European Union Agency for Asylum captured the point clearly: "The more EU systems are embedded into Tunisian operations, the more the EU shares the legal risk. We cannot claim it's their responsibility when our own surveillance feeds and operational planning are part of the process." The challenge is that this shared jurisdiction

¹⁵² Alice De Leo, "Fostering Accountability for Human Rights Violations in EU Externalization of Border Control," 7.

¹⁵³ *Hirsi Jamaa and Others v. Italy*, Application no. 27765/09, European Court of Human Rights, Judgment of 23 February 2012, art. 98.

¹⁵⁴ Emma Soltis, "Funding Repression: How the EU Migration Agreements with Libya and Tunisia Circumvent Non-Refoulement and Enable Human Rights Violations," 243.

¹⁵⁵ Isidoros Aivatidis, "A Change in the EU External Migration Policy? The EU–Tunisia Memorandum of Understanding as an Instrument of the New External Migration Paradigm," *College of Europe Research Paper* WP-96, 15-16.

exists in practice, but the accountability systems to support it are missing, leaving a difference between legal responsibility and the ability to make sure it is followed.

Monitoring and Transparency Deficits

The maritime control system operating off the Tunisian coast is marked by limited transparency and restricted access for independent observers. Humanitarian organisations are often denied entry to key border and port facilities, which prevents them from independently checking the conditions and treatment of people who are intercepted.¹⁵⁶ Without access, abuses remain unrecorded, and violations of due process or non-refoulement occur without documentation.

This restriction is not accidental but reflects a deliberate approach to governance. Informal coordination between state agencies and security forces allows operational decisions to be made without public scrutiny or the possibility of external review.¹⁵⁷ In this environment, oversight mechanisms exist nominally but lack the tools or information to intervene meaningfully.

The European Court of Auditors has noted that performance-based financing in migration control often prioritises measurable operational outputs, such as interception numbers, over qualitative indicators related to rights protection.¹⁵⁸ The result is that operational success is defined by boats stopped and people intercepted, while the question of what happens after interception remains invisible to both funders and the public.

Migrants intercepted at sea have in some cases been transported to Tunisia's desert borders and left without water or shelter, far from any legal authority or humanitarian assistance. These actions cannot be independently investigated without transparent access to the sites where individuals are held or transferred.

¹⁵⁶ Tove Lindgren-Jansson, "Trapped between Borders: Human Rights Consequences of EU Externalization in Libya and Tunisia," 45.

¹⁵⁷ Hamza Meddeb and Fakhreddine Louati, *Tunisia's Transformation Into a Transit Hub*, 18.

¹⁵⁸ European Court of Auditors, *Special Report 24/2021: Performance-Based Financing in Cohesion Policy: Worthy Ambitions, but Obstacles Remained in the 2014-2020 Period*, 16.

“We have repeatedly requested access to holding facilities in coastal towns,” said a migration health coordinator from Médecins Sans Frontières in Tunis, “but the doors remain closed to us. We know people are inside, but we are not allowed to assess their condition.”¹⁵⁹

A field coordinator from the Boat Refugee Foundation described similar barriers: “We have been present when boats arrived at port, but we were kept behind a barrier. We could not verify who was on board or whether anyone requested asylum.”¹⁶⁰ The absence of transparent monitoring structures allows such moments to pass without record, effectively removing them from the chain of accountability.

Sociological Impact of Accountability Gaps

The absence of independent monitoring does not only obscure legal violations, it also shapes the social and psychological realities of those affected. Without ways to check how people are treated or what happens after interception, individuals who may have legitimate protection claims are rendered invisible both legally and in humanitarian terms. This invisibility contributes to processes where people are treated mainly as security risks rather than as holders of rights.¹⁶¹ Once categorised in this way, their access to legal protections narrows, and their vulnerability to abuse and exploitation increases.

You meet people who have tried to claim asylum once, were turned away without explanation, and now refuse to go near any authority.¹⁶²

Meddeb and Louati describe how repeated interceptions and returns create cycles of displacement, where individuals are forced into increasingly dangerous routes and become more dependent on smugglers.¹⁶³ This pattern not only increases material insecurity but also weakens trust in institutions, making people less likely to seek help from official authorities even when they need it.

¹⁵⁹ Interview with Migration Health Coordinator, Doctors Without Borders (Médecins Sans Frontières), Tunis Office, conducted in English on 9 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁶⁰ Interview with Field Coordinator, Boat Refugee Foundation (Stichting Bootvluchteling), Lesbos Operations, conducted in English on 12 March 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, in Athens.

¹⁶¹ Vasja Badalič, “Tunisia’s Role in the EU External Migration Policy,” 92.

¹⁶² Interview with Protection Associate, UNHCR Tunisia Country Office, conducted in English on 7 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁶³ Hamza Meddeb and Fakhreddine Louati, *Tunisia’s Transformation Into a Transit Hub*, 21.

You start to see a kind of shutdown. People stop believing that they have any options left, and that has real mental health consequences.¹⁶⁴

Strik and Robbesom highlight that the absence of predictable rights pathways leaves individuals trapped in prolonged insecurity, unable to move forward or return safely.¹⁶⁵ In this environment, the lack of transparency in procedures is not an administrative oversight but a systemic condition that produces long-term instability.

We have treated the same people after three, four failed crossings. The physical injuries heal, but the mental exhaustion is harder to address. It's the hopelessness that stays.¹⁶⁶

The combination of opaque operations, absent monitoring, and weak legal recourse ensures that those intercepted at sea remain in a precarious position, both legally and socially. These are not incidental failings but structural conditions that produce sustained human insecurity.

Accountability will not appear by accident. It must be built into the operations.¹⁶⁷

If you cannot verify what happens after an interception, you cannot claim protection exists.¹⁶⁸

The lack of verification after interceptions shows how EU-funded coastal surveillance in Tunisia can operate without ensuring that non-refoulement and due process guarantees are respected. In practice, this means people are stopped, returned, and left without any way to have their case heard. The legal process ends before it begins. For the individuals affected, this is not just a technical failure, it changes their entire situation. Without recognition in the legal system, they have no status, no access to protection, and no way to challenge what has happened to them. This often forces them into repeated attempts to cross, exposes them to greater risks at sea, and leaves lasting effects on their physical and mental health. The result

¹⁶⁴ Interview with Regional Humanitarian Affairs Officer, International Rescue Committee (IRC), conducted in English on 3 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁶⁵ Tineke Strik and Ruben Robbesom, "Compliance or Complicity? An Analysis of the EU–Tunisia Deal in the Context of the Externalisation of Migration Control," 210.

¹⁶⁶ Interview with Migration Health Coordinator, Doctors Without Borders (Médecins Sans Frontières), Tunis Office, conducted in English on 9 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁶⁷ Interview with Legal Officer, European Asylum Support Office (EUAA), Operational Support Department, conducted in English on 16 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁶⁸ Interview with Field Coordinator, Boat Refugee Foundation (Stichting Bootvluchteling), Lesbos Operations, conducted in English on 12 March 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, in Athens.

is a system where interception success is measured, but the human impact of these operations is ignored.

CHAPTER 3: LIVED CONSEQUENCES OF BORDER CONTROL

The tightening of EU-funded maritime surveillance in Tunisia is often presented through operational statistics, political statements, or news coverage that frames interceptions as success stories in migration management. While these narratives dominate public discourse, the lived experiences of those who endure these interceptions remain largely absent. Direct testimony from intercepted migrants is not included in this research, but I have conducted interviews with humanitarian professionals who have been in close, repeated contact with affected individuals in both Tunisia and Europe. Their accounts provide an indirect but detailed insight into the realities that follow maritime control operations.

The humanitarians interviewed spoke of repeated encounters with people who had been intercepted, detained, expelled, or left in a state of legal invisibility. They described patterns of physical and psychological harm, disorientation from being moved between facilities without explanation, and the erosion of trust in any official process. This is not simply the outcome of individual incidents but the cumulative effect of a system where interception is efficient while rights protection remains inconsistent.

I have met people who have been through this cycle three or four times. Each time they come back with fewer belongings, more health problems, and less belief that their story will ever be heard.¹⁶⁹

In the following sections, I analyse these lived consequences through three themes. The first examines how interception and detention heighten vulnerability. The second explores the symbolic violence embedded in securitised border practices. The third addresses the long-term mental health and social marginalisation that result from repeated exclusion from due process. Together, these themes show how border control policies affect much more than just the sea, influencing the everyday lives and future opportunities of the people who are

¹⁶⁹ Interview with Regional Humanitarian Affairs Officer, International Rescue Committee (IRC), conducted in English on 3 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

intercepted.

3.1 Interceptions, Detention, and Migrant Vulnerability

Maritime interceptions off the Tunisian coast have become increasingly coordinated, supported by EU-funded patrol vessels, radar systems, and training programs. This operational expansion has significantly increased the number of boats stopped before reaching international waters, a development frequently highlighted in EU progress reports as an indicator of success.¹⁷⁰ However, measuring outcomes primarily by interception rates obscures the realities faced by those on board. Interception is not the end of a journey but the beginning of a new sequence of vulnerabilities that are deeply shaped by the absence of consistent legal safeguards and humanitarian protections.

Migrants assembled at a Tunisian port area following interception, awaiting processing or transfer. This image captures a moment of uncertainty that illustrates the growing emotional and legal limbo faced by many intercepted migrants. (Photo: Jihed Abidellaoui/Reuters)

In many cases, the first stage after interception is transfer to coastal holding facilities. These facilities vary in their conditions but are often temporary, overcrowded, and lack adequate medical care. Testimonies collected by humanitarian workers describe a process in which migrants are brought ashore, questioned briefly, and then either released without

¹⁷⁰ Emma Soltis, “Funding Repression,” 243.

documentation or transported inland with little explanation of their legal situation.¹⁷¹ Without a formal registration system in place, intercepted individuals can disappear from any official record, making it impossible to trace their case or ensure they have access to asylum procedures.¹⁷²

People arrive onshore believing they will be able to explain why they fled, but the reality is that nobody is listening. They are tired, frightened, and often do not even know where they are being taken.¹⁷³

Detention, whether formal or informal, is a recurring element in the post-interception process. While Tunisia has no dedicated immigration detention law, migrants are often held in police stations or other secured facilities for short periods under general public order provisions.¹⁷⁴ The lack of legal clarity over detention grounds means there is little judicial oversight, and access for independent monitors or lawyers is rare.¹⁷⁵ This creates a setting where individuals can be deprived of liberty without a formal charge, without knowing the duration of their detention, and without a chance to challenge it.

The EU's role in reinforcing these systems is indirect but substantial. Funding agreements specify capacity-building for Tunisian maritime authorities but do not require the establishment of procedures to guarantee due process for those intercepted. The result is a context in which operational capacity increases without a parallel strengthening of the rights infrastructure.

The system is built to move people quickly away from the coast, not to identify those who might need protection. Speed takes priority over rights.¹⁷⁶

Health and safety conditions during and after detention compound vulnerability. Intercepted individuals often arrive in poor physical condition after days at sea, with dehydration,

¹⁷¹ Fatma Raach, "Tunisia–EU Cooperation in Migration Management," 228.

¹⁷² Berfin Nur Osso, "Unpacking the Safe Third Country Concept in the European Union," 280.

¹⁷³ Interview with Protection Associate, UNHCR Tunisia Country Office, conducted in English on 7 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁷⁴ Giuffrè, Denaro, and Raach, "On 'Safety' and EU Externalization of Borders," 7.

¹⁷⁵ Hamza Meddeb and Fakhreddine Louati, *Tunisia's Transformation Into a Transit Hub*, 18.

¹⁷⁶ Interview with Regional Humanitarian Affairs Officer, International Rescue Committee (IRC), conducted in English on 3 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

hypothermia, or untreated injuries.¹⁷⁷ In the absence of systematic medical screening, some are released or expelled without receiving treatment. Humanitarian organisations working in Tunisia have documented cases of severe health deterioration after release, particularly when migrants are expelled to remote border regions where there is no immediate access to care.

Migrants' legal and physical insecurity is amplified by the practice of collective expulsions to desert border areas with Libya and Algeria. These expulsions, frequently carried out without any form of individual assessment, directly contradict the principle of non-refoulement and eliminate any opportunity to seek asylum.¹⁷⁸ The absence of interpreters during the interception and detention phases means that many do not even know they have the right to request protection.

I treated a young man who had been pushed across the border. He was exhausted, disoriented, and had not eaten for days. Nobody had asked him a single question about why he left his country.¹⁷⁹

The psychological impact of these processes is significant. Repeated interception and detention without clear procedures erode trust in any form of institutional assistance, leading many migrants to avoid official channels altogether.¹⁸⁰ This avoidance increases exposure to smuggling networks, where the risk of exploitation and abuse is high. Furthermore, the uncertainty and lack of agency experienced in detention contribute to long-term trauma, manifesting as anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress symptoms.¹⁸¹

From a sociological perspective, the combination of rapid operational action and minimal legal oversight shapes the lived reality of migrants in ways that extend far beyond the moment of interception. Those detained at sea often experience heightened anxiety, uncertainty, and physical hardship, while individuals expelled or released without documentation find themselves in precarious spaces where they lack protection, access to services, or the ability to assert their rights. These patterns are the outcome of a system in which border control

¹⁷⁷ Tove Lindgren-Jansson, "Trapped between Borders: Human Rights Consequences of EU Externalization in Libya and Tunisia," 2.

¹⁷⁸ Vasja Badalič, "Tunisia's Role in the EU External Migration Policy," 89.

¹⁷⁹ Interview with Migration Health Coordinator, Doctors Without Borders (Médecins Sans Frontières), Tunis Office, conducted in English on 9 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁸⁰ Hamza Meddeb and Fakhreddine Louati, *Tunisia's Transformation Into a Transit Hub*, 21.

¹⁸¹ Tineke Strik and Ruben Robbesom, "Compliance or Complicity? An Analysis of the EU-Tunisia Deal," 214.

measures take precedence over safeguarding individual well-being, creating environments that perpetuate marginalisation and erode resilience. In this sense, EU-funded coastal surveillance not only restricts mobility but actively contributes to the long-term social and legal exclusion of those it intercepts, reflecting a deeper departure from the protective aims of international and EU refugee law.

3.2 Symbolic Violence and the Securitization of Migrants

In Tunisia, the way migrants are spoken about and shown to the public often shapes their fate as much as the physical measures that stop them at sea. Narratives in politics and media frequently present migration as a problem to be contained, with an emphasis on control and security. Over time, this language and imagery create a climate in which harsh measures appear reasonable, even necessary, to protect public order. This is part of what sociologists describe as symbolic violence; the power to make unequal treatment seem natural and acceptable without the need for direct force.¹⁸²

Securitization is the process that drives this. It reframes migration as a security risk rather than a humanitarian concern. In Tunisia, this framing is reinforced by the language of migration agreements with the EU, which prioritise “managing flows” and “strengthening borders.” The people behind these statistics and policy goals become secondary to the objective of keeping movements under control.

This change in perception can be seen in how sub-Saharan migrants are often portrayed in Tunisian media. Coverage tends to focus on numbers, arrests, or “illegal” crossings, while rarely showing individual stories or exploring the reasons for migration.¹⁸³ These portrayals feed into public ideas of migrants as a faceless group rather than as individuals with specific needs and rights. Over time, this makes it easier for authorities to justify detention, forced relocation, and restrictions on movement without strong public resistance.

The symbolic dimension of control is also present in the safe third country designation applied to Tunisia. While this legal label suggests that returned migrants will receive adequate

¹⁸² Amal Hlioui, “Representations of Sub-Saharans in Tunisian Media,” 153.

¹⁸³ Monika Salzbrunn and Simon Mastrangelo, “Representations of Tunisian Undocumented Migration on the Internet,” 172.

protection, reports consistently show that conditions do not meet international standards. Yet the designation remains in use, acting as a powerful signal to the public and to European institutions that legal obligations are being met, even when evidence shows significant gaps.

When the state talks about you as a threat, even if you are just a person looking for safety, it changes how everyone else sees you. Landlords do not want to rent to you, employers avoid you, and the police feel justified in pushing you out. It is not only about the law...it is about the whole atmosphere.¹⁸⁴

Securitization also changes how migrants behave. Humanitarian staff describe how many avoid hospitals, shelters, or legal aid centres for fear that their presence will be reported to authorities. This avoidance keeps them outside formal systems, leaving them more vulnerable to exploitation and harm.¹⁸⁵

From the operational side, funding structures prioritise technical capacity and measurable outcomes, such as the number of interceptions, over softer indicators like the quality of legal access or the fairness of procedures. This emphasis reinforces the idea that migration is a logistical challenge rather than a matter of rights and protection.

If the story told to the public is that borders are under siege, then any amount of control seems justified...I have seen entire boat groups treated as if they were a single problem to be solved, not as human beings with different needs.¹⁸⁶

The daily reality for migrants under these conditions is one of constant caution. Many change their routes, travel at night, or move in small groups to avoid being noticed. While this can reduce the risk of interception, it increases exposure to other dangers such as unsafe work or reliance on smugglers.¹⁸⁷

I spoke to a young man who had been intercepted twice. The second time, he told me, he felt like he was being hunted. He avoided the city altogether, sleeping outside in an orchard so that no one could see him. It is a way of surviving, but it eats away at your

¹⁸⁴ Interview with Protection Associate, UNHCR Tunisia Country Office, conducted in English on 7 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁸⁵ Vasja Badalič, "Tunisia's Role in the EU External Migration Policy," 98.

¹⁸⁶ Interview with Regional Humanitarian Affairs Officer, International Rescue Committee (IRC), conducted in English on 3 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁸⁷ Hoffmann Pham and Komiyama, "Strategic Choices of Migrants and Smugglers in the Central Mediterranean Sea," 38.

mind.¹⁸⁸

Symbolic violence and securitization work together to shape the migrant experience in Tunisia. They influence how migrants are treated by authorities, how they are perceived by the public, and how they navigate their own survival. This dynamic not only justifies rapid and sometimes arbitrary enforcement measures but also creates a long-term environment in which exclusion and vulnerability are seen as normal outcomes of migration control.

3.3 Silencing, Marginalization, and Mental Health Outcomes

Silencing is not only the absence of voice, but the active removal of opportunities to be heard. In the context of EU-funded maritime control in Tunisia, this silencing is reinforced by the structures of interception and detention that prevent migrants from accessing lawyers, journalists, or independent monitors. Once detained, intercepted individuals often enter a closed system where there is no official record of their case, no formal recognition of their identity, and no pathway to challenge decisions made about them. This effectively erases them from legal and political visibility while leaving them fully exposed to physical and psychological harm.

The silencing operates on multiple levels. On the bureaucratic level, the absence of systematic registration means that many are never assigned a case file; without a file, there is no process to follow, no decision to appeal, and no way to engage the protection mechanisms promised under the 1951 Refugee Convention or the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. On the public level, strict media controls and restrictions on NGO access to ports and holding centres keep their experiences out of the national conversation.¹⁸⁹

You have to understand that once someone is in those facilities, they disappear from view. Even their friends and family do not know where they are. They can be moved at night, and no one is told. It is like they stop existing in the eyes of the outside world.¹⁹⁰

¹⁸⁸ Interview with Migration Health Coordinator, Doctors Without Borders (Médecins Sans Frontières), Tunis Office, conducted in English on 9 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁸⁹ Tove Lindgren-Jansson, “Trapped between Borders: Human Rights Consequences of EU Externalization in Libya and Tunisia,” 7.

¹⁹⁰ Interview with Protection Associate, UNHCR Tunisia Country Office, conducted in English on 7 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

A Sudanese refugee protests outside UNHCR headquarters in Tunis, Tunisia, demanding evacuation. Photo: Jihed Abidellaoui/Reuters.

This invisibility creates conditions for marginalization. Migrants, already excluded from formal employment and housing markets, are pushed further into informal and often exploitative labour arrangements. Landlords charge higher rents for unsafe, overcrowded rooms, employers withhold wages, and smugglers extract payments under the threat of violence.¹⁹¹ For women, this vulnerability often intersects with gender-based violence; humanitarian workers have reported cases of sexual assault by both employers and security personnel, with victims having no realistic avenue to report abuse without risking deportation.¹⁹²

From the perspective of mental health, prolonged marginalization without a sense of safety or future prospects is devastating. Clinical literature on forced migration consistently links such conditions to chronic anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder. In Tunisia, where migrants may be intercepted multiple times and face repeated cycles of detention, relocation, and attempted departure, these effects are compounded.¹⁹³

¹⁹¹ Hamza Meddeb and Fakhreddine Louati, *Tunisia's Transformation Into a Transit Hub*, 21.

¹⁹² Amnesty International, *Amnesty International Report 2022/23: The State of the World's Human Rights*, 14.

¹⁹³ Vasja Badalič, "Tunisia's Role in the EU External Migration Policy: Crimmigration Law, Illegal Practices, and Their Impact on Human Rights," 92.

We see people who have been intercepted three, four times. The last time they come back to us, they can barely speak. They just sit, staring. The hope is gone, and that is when the real danger starts, because without hope, people take more risks.¹⁹⁴

Silencing also occurs through fear. Many migrants avoid seeking legal assistance or medical help because they believe it will expose them to the authorities. This belief is not unfounded; in some cases, information shared with public hospitals has been used to locate and detain undocumented migrants. As a result, health problems go untreated until they become emergencies, and legal problems remain unresolved, further entrenching their precarious situation.¹⁹⁵

Marginalization is reinforced by the broader securitization narrative described earlier in this chapter. By portraying migrants as potential threats, public discourse legitimises exclusionary practices and discourages solidarity from host communities. The cycle becomes self-reinforcing: intercepted migrants are hidden from view, which makes their suffering invisible, which in turn prevents the public from questioning the policies that cause it.

Migrants stranded in the desert near the Libya-Tunisia border after being expelled, showing the physical isolation and vulnerability they endure. (Photo: Hazem Ahmed/Reuters)

¹⁹⁴ Interview with Migration Health Coordinator, Doctors Without Borders (Médecins Sans Frontières), Tunis Office, conducted in English on 9 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

¹⁹⁵ Tineke Strik and Ruben Robbesom, “Compliance or Complicity?,” 212.

There are people in the desert who have not spoken to anyone in days. The isolation is not just physical; it is like their story has been cut off. No one will hear what happened to them unless we take it back ourselves.¹⁹⁶

The mental health consequences of this enforced invisibility are significant. Humanitarian organisations working in Tunisia report high levels of sleep disturbance, panic attacks, and symptoms of complex trauma among migrants who have been through multiple interceptions. In some cases, these symptoms are so severe that individuals become unable to make decisions about their next steps, effectively immobilising them in dangerous environments.

Another layer of marginalization is the erosion of agency. When migrants are intercepted and relocated without explanation or choice, it sends a powerful message that they have no control over their own lives. This lack of agency is itself a predictor of poor mental health outcomes, as it undermines the sense of self-efficacy needed to recover from trauma.¹⁹⁷

A man told me once that it is better to drown than to be sent back again, because at least then the decision is yours. That is what loss of control does...it makes death seem like the only choice you get to make.¹⁹⁸

Legal status is often determined at the moment of interception, without adequate opportunity for asylum claims or legal review. Once excluded from formal processes, individuals have no realistic way to regularise their status, leaving them in perpetual legal limbo. This limbo exacerbates mental distress by creating a state of “frozen futures” where no progress or resolution is possible.¹⁹⁹

The silence extends to the international level. While the EU funds and coordinates aspects of Tunisia’s coastal surveillance, there is little transparency about what happens to those intercepted. Without public reporting or independent monitoring, there is no sustained pressure to change practices that harm mental health and violate due process.²⁰⁰

¹⁹⁶ Interview with Field Coordinator, Boat Refugee Foundation (Stichting Bootvluchteling), Lesbos Operations, conducted in English on 12 March 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, in Athens.

¹⁹⁷ Katharina Natter, “Tunisia’s Migration Politics throughout the 2011 Revolution: Revisiting the Democratisation-Migrant Rights Nexus,” 1560.

¹⁹⁸ Interview with Field Coordinator, Boat Refugee Foundation (Stichting Bootvluchteling), Lesbos Operations, conducted in English on 12 March 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, in Athens.

¹⁹⁹ Jean-Pierre Cassarino, “Channelled Policy Transfers: EU-Tunisia Interactions on Migration Matters,” 102.

²⁰⁰ European Court of Auditors, *Special Report*, 16.

It is not just that people are detained or expelled...it is that no one outside even knows it happened. If you cannot see a problem, you cannot fix it.²⁰¹

These conditions include legal invisibility, physical isolation, fear of contact with authorities, and a lack of agency. Together, they interact to produce deep and lasting harm. This harm is not incidental to border control efforts. It is the result of a system that prioritises the number of interceptions over meeting protection obligations. The impact is not only felt on an individual level. It extends to entire migrant communities, who adapt to life in hiding. Their social relationships, economic survival strategies, and even their sense of identity are shaped by the need to stay out of sight.

²⁰¹ Interview with Legal Officer, European Asylum Support Office (EUAA), Operational Support Department, conducted in English on 16 June 2025 by Kristina Stolbova, via Google Meet.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this thesis demonstrate that the cooperation between the European Union and Tunisia on border control is more than a logistical arrangement for maritime interception. It is a policy framework that decisively shapes the rights, status, and lived experiences of migrants in transit. While the agreements governing this cooperation contain language that references protection obligations under international and EU law, the evidence shows that these protections are largely absent in practice. The result is an operational system that increases interception capacity but leaves significant gaps in legal protections and humanitarian oversight.

Across the preceding chapters, the legal analysis made clear that the principle of non-refoulement, recognised in the 1951 Refugee Convention and reinforced in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, cannot function without concrete procedural guarantees. Sources consistently identify individual risk assessments, access to legal advice, interpretation in a language understood by the applicant, the prohibition of collective expulsions, and the right to judicial review with suspensive effect as necessary preconditions for meaningful protection.²⁰² In the Tunisian context, these guarantees remain largely aspirational. Interceptions frequently occur without individual assessment, and legal assistance is rarely available when people are brought ashore. The absence of a national asylum law leaves migrants relying on temporary procedures managed by international organisations, which have limited reach and no legal authority over state authorities.²⁰³

The lack of enforceable oversight adds to these problems. Parliamentary review in Tunisia is weak, judicial review is almost entirely absent in migration cases, and the EU's accountability structures focus on project outputs rather than actual rights protections.²⁰⁴ Informal cooperation agreements often operate outside formal accountability systems,

²⁰² Giuffré, Denaro, and Raach, "On 'Safety' and EU Externalization of Borders," 7; Berfin Nur Osso, "Unpacking the Safe Third Country Concept in the European Union," 280.

²⁰³ Fatma Raach, "Tunisia-EU Cooperation in Migration Management," 228.

²⁰⁴ European Court of Auditors, *Special Report*, 16.

allowing for rapid operational implementation but limiting opportunities for legal challenge. In the EU-Tunisia partnership, performance is measured by reductions in departures rather than adherence to protection obligations.

The EU's financial and operational role gives it a level of responsibility recognized under human rights law, including the reasoning in *Hirsi Jamaa v. Italy*. By funding, supporting, and sometimes guiding Tunisia's maritime operations, the EU has practical control over actions that directly affect the rights of individuals.²⁰⁵ This means that the EU cannot absolve itself of responsibility for violations occurring within joint or EU-supported operations. Nonetheless, the institutional practice has been to treat Tunisia as solely responsible for any abuses, effectively creating a gap in accountability that leaves victims with no way to challenge or seek remedy for violations.

The sociological consequences of this policy model are severe and well-documented. Interviews and secondary sources reveal that interception is often the beginning of a cycle of repeated detention, expulsion, and re-attempted departure, with each iteration increasing the vulnerability of those involved. Migrants who are expelled without documentation face immediate risks in transit zones, including exposure to violence, theft, and sexual assault. Women and children are particularly at risk, with gender-based violence frequently going unreported due to fear of deportation.²⁰⁶

This condition of legal invisibility has a lasting impact on migrants' capacity to build a secure life. Without recognised status, they are excluded from formal employment and housing, forcing reliance on informal networks that are often exploitative. Economic marginalisation intersects with social exclusion, as securitised narratives portray migrants as a threat to public order, reducing the likelihood of community support.²⁰⁷ Over time, this exclusion leads to isolation and weakens social cohesion within migrant communities, as trust in institutions and even in humanitarian organisations declines.²⁰⁸

²⁰⁵ Alice De Leo, "Fostering Accountability for Human Rights Violations in EU Externalization of Border Control," 7.

²⁰⁶ Amnesty International, *Amnesty International Report 2022/23: The State of the World's Human Rights*, 14.

²⁰⁷ Amal Hlioui, "Representations of Sub-Saharan in Tunisian Media," 180.

²⁰⁸ Tineke Strik and Ruben Robbesom, "Compliance or Complicity?," 210.

Mental health deterioration emerges as a direct consequence of these conditions. The “crimmigration” dynamic, where migration control is framed primarily as a matter of law enforcement, creating a persistent environment of fear and instability. Clinical literature on forced migration links this type of prolonged uncertainty to chronic anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder.²⁰⁹ In Tunisia, repeated interceptions without a path to legal resolution produce a state of “frozen futures” in which individuals are unable to plan or take meaningful action towards stability. This state is more than an accidental result of policy and is a condition built into a system that measures success through deterrence.

Symbolic violence reinforces these patterns by framing intercepted individuals as potential criminals or security threats, which legitimises policies that limit their visibility in public spaces and restrict their access to services.²¹⁰ Restrictions on NGO access to detention facilities and landing areas ensure that the human consequences of these policies remain largely undocumented. This enforced invisibility prevents the development of political pressure for reform, as abuses cannot provoke public reaction if they are not publicly known.

The combined legal and sociological findings point to a governance model that is structurally resistant to accountability. Informal agreements and funding tied to operational results avoid the constraints of binding legal obligations while making sure that operational targets are met. Monitoring mechanisms, when they exist, often rely on the cooperation of the same authorities whose actions they are supposed to oversee. As a result of the arrangement, interceptions rise, protection standards stay the same, and the well-being of migrants suffers.

From a broader perspective, the EU-Tunisia cooperation represents a key part of European migration policy focused on externalising border control. In practice, this means the EU extends its influence over migration by supporting Tunisian authorities to intercept, monitor, and manage migrants before they reach EU territory. At the same time, the EU limits its own legal responsibility for how these migrants are treated once in Tunisia. As a result, the EU can claim progress in border management while serious gaps in human rights protection and access to asylum for migrants in Tunisia continue to persist.

²⁰⁹ Vasja Badalič, “Tunisia’s Role in the EU External Migration Policy,” 92.

²¹⁰ Teresa Cappiali and Agnese Pacciardi, “Reorienting EU Border Externalization Studies,” 312.

The central finding of this thesis is that the operational success of EU-funded coastal surveillance in Tunisia is inseparable from the protection failures documented here. The ability to intercept more vessels at sea, without parallel investment in fair asylum procedures and independent oversight, creates a cycle of harm that weakens both the intent and the legal standards of international protection norms. Migrants face immediate risks during and after interception, long-term exclusion from legal status, and sustained psychological harm. These are not isolated or accidental outcomes but foreseeable consequences of the way the cooperation is designed and implemented.

Any reform of this system would require a fundamental rebalancing of priorities. Protection must be an integral part of operations, included as a standard requirement rather than something secondary. Funding agreements should make payments dependent on both the number of interceptions and whether protection rules are properly followed. Independent monitoring should have full access to all landing sites, detention centers, and deportation locations, with their findings published to ensure real accountability.

The EU cannot claim to uphold its legal and moral commitments to refugees and asylum seekers while maintaining a partnership that enables systematic violations of those commitments. Tunisia, for its part, must develop the institutional capacity and legal framework necessary to process asylum claims fairly and transparently. Without such reforms, the cooperation will continue to produce the dual harm of legal dispossession and social marginalisation for those intercepted.

The evidence shows that externalisation in its current form creates a managed invisibility that serves political and operational goals while silencing those most affected. The harm is measurable, foreseeable, and avoidable. Addressing it will require political will, institutional reform, and a shift in the metrics by which success is judged. Until such changes occur, the cooperation will remain a policy that secures borders at the expense of human life and dignity, with consequences that extend far beyond the point of interception.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Aivatidis, Isidoros. “A Change in the EU External Migration Policy? The EU-Tunisia Memorandum of Understanding as an Instrument of the New External Migration Paradigm.” *College of Europe Research Paper* WP-96, 2024. https://www.coleurope.eu/sites/default/files/research-paper/wp96_AIVATIDIS_02_0.pdf.
- Amnesty International. *Amnesty International Report 2022/23: The State of the World's Human Rights*. London: Amnesty International Ltd, 2023. ISBN 978-0-86210-502-0; Index: POL 10/5670/2023. <https://www.amnesty.org/en/documents/pol10/5670/2023/en/>.
- Amnesty International. *Tunisia: Amnesty International's Secretary General Denounces Rollback of Human Rights upon Concluding Four-Day Visit*. London: Amnesty International, July 26, 2024. <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2024/07/tunisia-amnesty-secretary-general-denounces-rollback-human-rights/>.
- Badalič, Vasja. “Tunisia’s Role in the EU External Migration Policy: Crimmigration Law, Illegal Practices, and Their Impact on Human Rights.” *Journal of International Migration and Integration* 20, no. 1: 85-100, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12134-018-0596-7>.
- Bartels, Inken. “Practices and Power of Knowledge Dissemination in International Organizations in the Externalization of Migration Management in Morocco and Tunisia.” *Movements: Journal for Critical Migration and Border Regime Studies* 4, no. 1, 2018. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/304636200_For_the_Benefit_of_Some_The_International_Organization_for_Migration_and_its_Global_Migration_Management.

- Cappiali, Teresa, and Agnese Pacciardi. "Reorienting EU Border Externalization Studies: A Decolonial Intersectional Approach." *Geopolitics* 30, no. 1: 300-324, 2025. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/14650045.2024.2311175>.
- Cassarino, Jean-Pierre. "Channelled Policy Transfers: EU–Tunisia Interactions on Migration Matters." *European Journal of Migration and Law* 16: 97-123, 2014. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/270538342_Channelled_Policy_Transfers_EU-Tunisia_Interactions_on_Migration_Matters.
- Cuttitta, Paolo. "Non-governmental/Civil Society Organisations and the European Union-externalisation of Migration Management in Tunisia and Egypt." *Population, Space and Place* 26, no. 7: 1-13, 2020. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1002/psp.2329>.
- De Leo, Alice. "Fostering Accountability for Human Rights Violations in EU Externalization of Border Control." *Journal of Borderlands Studies*, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15562948.2024.2382465>.
- European Commission. *A European Agenda on Migration*. COM(2015) 240 final. Brussels: European Commission, 13 May 2015. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52015DC0240>.
- European Commission. *Annex II: Action Document for EU Support to Border Management Institutions in Libya and Tunisia*. Annex to Commission Implementing Decision C(2021) 9615. Brussels: European Commission, 2021. https://enlargement.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-12/C_2021_9615_F1_ANNEX_EN_V3_P1_1639231%20Annex%20II%20BM%20LY%20TU.PDF.
- European Commission. *EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa: Objectives and Governance*. Brussels: European Commission, n.d. https://trust-fund-for-africa.europa.eu/index_en.
- European Commission. "EU Support to Migration-Related Activities in Tunisia." *Factsheet*, June 2023. Brussels: European Commission. https://enlargement.ec.europa.eu/factsheet-eu-support-migration-tunisia_en.

European Commission. “The European Union and Tunisia: Political Agreement on a Comprehensive Partnership Package.” Statement, 16 July 2023. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/statement_23_3881.

European Council on Refugees and Exiles (ECRE). “Policy Note #34.” Brussels: ECRE, 2021. <https://ecre.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Policy-Note-34.pdf>.

European Court of Auditors. *Special Report 17/2024: The EU Trust Fund for Africa-Despite New Approaches, Support Remained Unfocused*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2024. https://www.eca.europa.eu/ECAPublications/SR-2024-17/SR-2024-17_EN.pdf.

European Court of Auditors. *Special Report 24/2021: Performance-Based Financing in Cohesion Policy: Worthy Ambitions, but Obstacles Remained in the 2014-2020 Period*. Luxembourg: European Court of Auditors, 2021. https://www.eca.europa.eu/Lists/ECADocuments/SR21_24/SR_Performance_incentivisation_EN.pdf.

European Union. *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*. Official Journal of the European Union C 326: 391-407, 26 October 2012. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:12012P/TXT>.

European Union. *Consolidated Versions of the Treaty on European Union and of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union*. Official Journal of the European Union C 115, Luxembourg: Publications Office, 9 May 2008. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:12008M/TXT>.

García Andrade, Paula, and Eleonora Frasca. “The Memorandum of Understanding between the EU and Tunisia: Issues of Procedure and Substance on the Informalisation of Migration Cooperation.” *EU Immigration and Asylum Law and Policy* (blog), 26 January 2024. <https://eumigrationlawblog.eu/the-memorandum-of-understanding-between-the-eu-and-tunisia-issues-of-procedure-and-substance-on-the-informalisation-of-migration-cooperation/>.

- Giuffré, Mariagiulia, Chiara Denaro, and Fatma Raach. “On ‘Safety’ and EU Externalization of Borders: Questioning the Role of Tunisia as a ‘Safe Country of Origin’ and a ‘Safe Third Country.’” *European Journal of Migration and Law* 24, no. 4: 1-36, 2022. https://brill.com/view/journals/emil/24/4/article-p570_5.xml?ebody=pdf-130820.
- Helena Dalli. “Speech by High Representative/Vice-President Josep Borrell at EP Plenary on the Situation in the Country.” Strasbourg, October 22, 2024. European External Action Service. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/tunisia-speech-high-representativevice-president-jos-ep-borrell-ep-plenary-situation-country_en.
- Hlioui, Amal. “Representations of Sub-Saharanans in Tunisian Media: Silence, Othering, Dehumanisation and Collectivisation.” PhD diss., University of Palermo, 2024. <https://core.ac.uk/download/621426911.pdf>.
- Hoffmann Pham, Katherine, and Junpei Komiyama. “Strategic Choices of Migrants and Smugglers in the Central Mediterranean Sea.” 14 April 2024. <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0300553>.
- Lindgren-Jansson, Tove. “Trapped between Borders: Human Rights Consequences of EU Externalization in Libya and Tunisia.” Master’s thesis, Mid Sweden University, 2025. <https://fhs.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1937875/FULLTEXT01.pdf>.
- Meddeb, Hamza, and Fakhreddine Louati. *Tunisia’s Transformation Into a Transit Hub: Illegal Migration and Policy Dilemmas*. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, 27 March 2024. https://carnegie-production-assets.s3.amazonaws.com/static/files/Hamza_Migration-1.pdf.
- Natter, Katharina. “Tunisia’s Migration Politics throughout the 2011 Revolution: Revisiting the Democratisation-Migrant Rights Nexus.” *Third World Quarterly* 43, no. 7: 1551-69, 2022. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/01436597.2021.1940126>.

- Osso, Berfin Nur. “Unpacking the Safe Third Country Concept in the European Union: B/orders, Legal Spaces, and Asylum in the Shadow of Externalization.” *International Journal of Refugee Law* 35, no. 3: 272-303, October 2023. <https://academic.oup.com/ijrl/article/35/3/272/7477630?login=false>.
- Raach, Fatma. “Tunisia-EU Cooperation in Migration Management.” In *Selected Political, Legal, and Financial Instruments regarding Asylum, Protection, and Mobility between Tunisia and the EU*. Springer, 2024. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-74866-0_13.
- Salzbrunn, Monika, and Simon Mastrangelo. “Representations of Tunisian Undocumented Migration on the Internet: Methodological Approaches to a Digital Anthropology of Facebook.” In *7 Representations of Tunisian Undocumented Migration on the Internet*, 169-198. Peter Lang, 2022. <https://iris.unil.ch/entities/publication/d50cd670-8a1e-4975-a43e-4514bfb049cf>.
- Sha’ath, Hiba, and Fatma Raach. “Cooperation within Reason: Tunisia’s Approach to Asylum and Readmission.” *European Journal of Migration and Law* 26: 179-19, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718166-12340176>.
- Soltis, Emma. *The Price of Complicity: Tunisia–EU Partnership Agreement Fuels Serious Abuses Against Refugees, Asylum-seekers, and Migrants*. Geneva: International Commission of Jurists, 2024. https://www.icj.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/TUN-The-Price-of-Complicity-FIN_AL_compressed-1.pdf.
- Soltis, Emma. “Funding Repression: How the EU Migration Agreements with Libya and Tunisia Circumvent Non-Refoulement and Enable Human Rights Violations.” *Brooklyn Journal of International Law* 50: 238-278, 2025. <https://brooklynworks.brooklaw.edu/bjil/vol50/iss2/5>.
- Statewatch. “Parliamentary Lawyers: Democratic Oversight Needed for EU–Tunisia Migration Agreement.” 15 March 2024.

<https://www.statewatch.org/news/2024/march/parliamentary-lawyers-democratic-oversight-needed-for-eu-tunisia-migration-agreement/>.

Strik, Tineke, and Ruben Robbesom. “Compliance or Complicity? An Analysis of the EU–Tunisia Deal in the Context of the Externalisation of Migration Control.” *European Journal of Migration and Law*: 199-225, 2024. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/380094743_Compliance_or_Complicity_An_Analysis_of_the_EU-Tunisia_Deal_in_the_Context_of_the_Externalisation_of_Migration_Control.

Tahrir Institute for Middle East Policy. *Externalizing Migration Control to the MENA Region: Tunisia*. May 2025. <https://timep.org/2025/05/01/externalizing-migration-control-to-the-mena-region-tunisia/>.

United Nations. *Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees*. Adopted 28 July 1951; entered into force 22 April 1954. Geneva: United Nations. <https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/refugees.pdf>.

United Nations General Assembly. “Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration.” A/RES/73/195, 19 December 2018. New York: United Nations, 2019. https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/migration/generalassembly/docs/globalcompact/A_RES_73_195.pdf.

United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). *The 1951 Convention and 1967 Protocol Relating to the Status of Refugees*. Geneva: UNHCR, 2010. <https://www.unhcr.org/media/1951-refugee-convention-and-1967-protocol-relating-status-refugees>.

United Nations Human Rights Council. *Report of the Special Rapporteur on the Human Rights of Migrants, François Crépeau-Mission to Tunisia (3-8 June 2012)*. A/HRC/23/46/Add.1. Geneva: United Nations, 3 May 2013. <https://docs.un.org/en/A/HRC/23/46/Add.3>.

Yang, Yiran, Frederik Zuiderveen Borgesius, Pascal Beckers, and Evelien Brouwer. "Automated Decision-Making and Artificial Intelligence at European Borders and Their Risks for Human Rights." *Computer Law & Security Review* 52: 1-37, 2024. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/385176961_Automated_decision-making_and_artificial_intelligence_at_European_borders_and_their_risks_for_human_rights.

INTERVIEWS

Nr.	Date (2025)	Full Name / Affiliation	Role / Profession	Length (min)
1	30 January	JHA Counselor, Permanent Representation of the Netherlands to the EU	Justice and Home Affairs Section	30 min
2	12 March	Field Coordinator, Boat Refugee Foundation	Lesbos Operations	60 min
3	3 June	Regional Humanitarian Affairs Officer, International Rescue Committee (IRC)	Humanitarian Affairs	60 min
4	5 June	Legal Officer, DG Migration and Home Affairs, European Commission	Schengen and External Borders	30 min
5	6 June	Legal Advisor, VluchtelingenWerk Nederland	Dutch Council for Refugees	60 min
6	7 June	Protection Associate, UNHCR Tunisia Country Office	Protection	60 min
7	9 June	Migration Health Coordinator, Doctors Without Borders (MSF), Tunis Office	Health & Migration	60 min
8	12 June	Senior Legal Advisor, Fundamental Rights Agency of the EU (FRA)	Asylum and Migration	30 min
9	16 June	Legal Officer, European Asylum Support Office (EUAA)	Operational Support	60 min

Note: Most of the interviews were conducted through written correspondence. The transcripts presented here are based on the most relevant and insightful information provided by the interviewees and have been rewritten in a conversational format for clarity and coherence.

For a full transcript of interviews see Annex.

Outsourcing Responsibility:

*Non-Refoulement, Due Process, and the Human Consequences of EU–Tunisia
Border Cooperation*

ANNEX

Interview Transcripts

MA Thesis European Studies
European Policy Track

by

Kristina Stolbova

UNIVERSITY
OF AMSTERDAM

Graduate School for Humanities

2025

Student number: 15668371
Supervisor: Dr. Maciej Krogel
Second reader: Dr. Matteo Fermeglia

**Interview Transcript 1: Field
Coordinator, Boat Refugee
Foundation (Lesbos Operations)**

**Interview conducted in English on 12
March 2025 in Athens
Duration: 60 minutes**

Q: Can you describe your experience on the ground during maritime interceptions?

A: We have been present when boats arrived at port, but we were kept behind a barrier. We could not verify who was on board or whether anyone requested asylum. If you cannot verify what happens after an interception, you cannot claim protection exists.

Q: How does this affect the people intercepted?

A: There are people in the desert who have not spoken to anyone in days. The isolation is not just physical...it is like their story has been cut off. No one will hear what happened to them unless we take it back ourselves.

Q: What do intercepted individuals tell you about their mental state?

A: A man told me once that it is better to drown than to be sent back again, because at least then the decision is yours. That is what loss of control does...it makes death seem like the only choice you get to make.

Q: What does your organization focus on during emergencies?

A: Our focus is mainly on medical aid and mental health support. When boats arrive, people are often in shock, dehydrated, or injured. We try to give first aid quickly, but it's difficult when we don't even know how many people are on board or where they are taken.

Q: How do you see externalization policies affecting migrants' daily lives?

A: It makes everything harder. People don't know where they will end up. They live with

fear...not just of being intercepted, but of being sent somewhere they cannot survive. It also creates more hiding, more silence. People stop asking for help.

Q: What worries you most when you hear about return operations?

A: The speed. People are intercepted and moved fast. There is no time to explain their story, no time for a lawyer. Once they are on a bus or a plane, that's it. You don't know if they were sick, if they were a minor, if they had a valid claim.

Q: Have you seen changes in how the authorities behave during interceptions?

A: Yes. There's more coordination and more surveillance. But I wouldn't say that's made it safer for migrants. It's become more controlled, but not more humane. We still don't know where some people end up after interception.

Q: What kind of coordination do you have with EU institutions?

A: It's very limited. Sometimes we share health alerts or try to flag urgent cases, but we are not part of the official coordination. We often feel like observers—trying to help where we can, but not being given real access.

Q: In your view, which rights are most at risk in externalization deals?

A: The right to ask for asylum, definitely. Also the right to be treated as a human being. When control becomes the priority, care and fairness fall behind. People are treated like numbers, not individuals.

Q: What would make things better for migrants after arrival?

A: The most basic thing would be proper information. Let people know their rights, where they are, what will happen next. Right now, people arrive and get moved quickly without being told anything. That creates fear and confusion.

Q: How do you try to support people after interception?

A: We try to find them, follow up, offer health checks. But it's hard when you don't know where they were taken. Sometimes families call us asking, "Did you see my brother?" and we have no answers.

Q: How would you describe your access to detention facilities?

A: We are not allowed in. We have asked many times. We know people are inside, but we

can't check on them. We worry especially about kids and sick people. It's like a black box...once they go in, they disappear from sight.

Q: What kind of emotional state are people in after repeated interceptions?

A: Broken. That's the word. After the third or fourth time, many stop talking. Some cry for hours. Others don't say anything. They have lost everything and feel like no one cares.

**Interview Transcript 2: Senior Legal
Advisor, Fundamental Rights Agency
of the EU (FRA)**

**Interview conducted in English on 12
June 2025 via Google Meet
Duration: 30 minutes**

Q: How would you describe the current legal environment surrounding EU-Tunisia cooperation?

A: The legal framework is written to look clear and neutral, but it is applied in a very political environment.

Q: Are human rights protections consistently built into interception operations?

A: The infrastructure built with EU funds did not include a systematic mechanism for assessing protection needs during interception. That gap left space for practices that, in effect, bypassed due process guarantees.

Q: What are the implications of operating without a national asylum framework in Tunisia?

A: The absence of a statutory asylum procedure means EU actors rely on Tunisian capacity that doesn't exist in law, and that is a fundamental legal vulnerability.

Q: How do you describe the current accountability gap?

A: It creates a grey zone where significant operational powers are exercised without the normal checks that would accompany such authority within EU borders.

Q: What happens when operations prioritize numbers over process?

A: When interception targets dominate operational planning, screening and remedy fall behind the curve, creating a clear due-process gap because people are often returned or transferred before they have a meaningful chance to present asylum claims, access legal advice, or challenge removal decisions.

Q: What role do NGOs play on the ground?

A: The way the money is channelled really matters...having a strong NGO presence can reduce harm on the ground, but it is no replacement for a functioning state asylum and protection system.

Q: How do EU-Tunisian operational meetings usually unfold?

A: Our Tunisian counterparts are fully aware of the human rights clauses in the agreements, but in operational meetings the discussion turns quickly to patrol schedules and equipment status.

Q: Can you describe coordination challenges in protection screening?

A: It's a chain with missing links, where everyone assumes someone else is handling rights checks, so in the end, no one does it consistently.

Q: What legal risks come from relying on operational cooperation without formal procedures?

A: You end up with responsibility but no structure. When something goes wrong, it is hard to say who should fix it because no one is clearly in charge of the rights side of the operation.

Q: How do political priorities influence legal safeguards?

A: Political pressure often leads to faster action, but that speed can bypass legal review. What should be done carefully becomes something that is done quickly, and that is where mistakes happen.

Q: Are there any signs of improvement in how rights are handled in operations?

A: In some pilot projects yes, but they are the exception. Most of the time, rights protections remain secondary to logistical goals like stopping departures or increasing returns.

Q: How do partner states respond when rights issues are raised?

A: They often say it is not their responsibility, or they point to the EU. The EU in turn points back. That creates a situation where accountability goes in circles.

Q: Do you think rights training changes outcomes on the ground?

A: It helps in principle but it is not enough. You can train someone on paper standards but if the structure around them rewards speed and control that is what they will focus on.

Q: What role does FRA play in advising on these operations?

A: We provide legal guidance and review practices but we do not have enforcement power. Our reports can raise concerns but it is up to institutions and governments to act on them.

Q: What is the biggest misconception about EU-funded border work?

A: That it is just support. In reality funding shapes what happens, how people are treated, what gets prioritized. Money is not neutral, it influences choices and outcomes.

Q: Are migrants aware of their legal rights in these situations?

A: Very rarely. Most are confused and scared. Even when rights information is posted it is often in the wrong language or it comes too late to help.

Q: What challenges exist in documenting abuses or violations?

A: Access is a major issue. If NGOs and monitors cannot get into detention sites or ports it becomes very hard to collect reliable evidence or even know who is inside.

Q: What does the lack of a national asylum system mean for due process?

A: It means people have nowhere to go. Even if they want to claim asylum there is no official door to knock on. That is a major problem for legal accountability.

Q: How do you assess the design of externalization frameworks from a legal perspective?

A: They often lack enforcement tools. Even when there are rights clauses there is no built-in way to make sure they are followed or to check what happens when they are not.

Q: How does this affect trust in EU institutions?

A: It damages credibility. When we say human rights are central but then support systems that ignore them in practice it sends a mixed message to the public and to our partners.

Q: What kinds of reforms would make a difference?

A: Real-time monitoring, mandatory reporting, legal aid at arrival, and protection

assessments before return decisions. These are not complicated but they need political backing.

Q: Do operational staff have enough guidance on rights standards?

A: Often not. They are briefed on logistics not law. That is a gap. You cannot expect people to protect rights if they do not know what is required or if no one checks whether they did.

Q: How does externalization change the role of the EU in border control?

A: It moves the EU's influence beyond its borders but not its full responsibility. That creates an imbalance because the EU shapes outcomes without always being held accountable for them.

**Interview Transcript 3: Legal Officer,
European Asylum Support Office
(EUAA), Operational Support
Department**

Interview conducted in English on 16

June 2025 via Google Meet

Duration: 60 minutes

Q: What are the main challenges in monitoring compliance with non-refoulement in joint operations?

A: Monitoring compliance with non-refoulement in joint operations was a persistent difficulty, particularly because the EU's role was often presented as purely technical, even when the funding and equipment shaped the outcomes.

Q: What would improve the effectiveness of these joint operations?

A: Operational cooperation works best where national asylum procedures are present at the point of disembarkation, a condition not fully met in Tunisia.

Q: Do funding and logistics guarantee fair treatment?

A: Even when reception and referral systems have plenty of funding, they still often run without clear rules to follow.

Q: How would you describe the coordination on the ground?

A: Informal understandings between agencies that move faster than the law can catch up.

Q: What happens to intercepted people at the port?

A: Once a group is brought to shore, the immediate priority is clearing the port for the next operation; the legal checks can be delayed or skipped entirely if resources are stretched.

Q: What happens when migrants try to claim asylum?

A: When migrants ask who will hear their claim and no one has a clear answer.

Q: How does EU involvement impact accountability?

A: The more EU systems are embedded into Tunisian operations, the more the EU shares the legal risk. We cannot claim it's their responsibility when our own surveillance feeds and operational planning are part of the process.

Q: What needs to change for better accountability?

A: Accountability will not appear by accident. It must be built into the operations.

Q: What happens in cases of detention or expulsion?

A: It is not just that people are detained or expelled...it is that no one outside even knows it happened. If you cannot see a problem, you cannot fix it.

**Interview Transcript 4: Migration
Health Coordinator, Doctors Without
Borders (MSF), Tunis Office**

**Interview conducted in English on 9
June 2025 via Google Meet
Duration: 60 minutes**

Q: How would you describe the conditions of people intercepted at sea and returned to Tunisia?

A: You cannot speak about legal guarantees when people are being left in areas where survival is uncertain.

Q: Do people attempt the journey more than once?

A: We see the same people attempting the crossing again and again, but each time they return in worse physical and mental condition.

Q: What is your access like to detention or holding facilities?

A: We have repeatedly requested access to holding facilities in coastal towns, but the doors remain closed to us. We know people are inside, but we are not allowed to assess their condition.

Q: Can you share an example of someone who was pushed back?

A: I treated a young man who had been pushed across the border. He was exhausted, disoriented, and had not eaten for days. Nobody had asked him a single question about why he left his country.

Q: Do you hear stories of fear after interception?

A: I spoke to a young man who had been intercepted twice. The second time, he told me, he felt like he was being hunted. He avoided the city altogether, sleeping outside in an orchard so that no one could see him. It is a way of surviving, but it eats away at your mind.

Q: What do repeated interceptions do to people psychologically?

A: We see people who have been intercepted three, four times. The last time they come back to us, they can barely speak. They just sit, staring. The hope is gone, and that is when the real danger starts, because without hope, people take more risks.

**Interview Transcript 5: Regional
Humanitarian Affairs Officer,
International Rescue Committee
(IRC)**

**Interview conducted in English on 3
June 2025 via Google Meet
Duration: 60 minutes**

Q: How do you see capacity changes affecting border control?

A: Capacity has gone up, but without the procedural safeguards in place, interception becomes a tool of exclusion rather than protection.

Q: What are the biggest weaknesses you observe in the system?

A: The system works well for fast interceptions and transfers, but that efficiency is not matched by efficiency in informing people of their rights or giving them a fair hearing.

Q: What is the role of legal review?

A: Legal review is simply not part of the process; the focus is on clearing the ports for the next arrival, not on holding hearings.

Q: What psychological effect does this have on people?

A: You start to see a kind of shutdown. People stop believing that they have any options left, and that has real mental health consequences.

Q: What do you notice in people who go through the cycle repeatedly?

A: I have met people who have been through this cycle three or four times. Each time they come back with fewer belongings, more health problems, and less belief that their story will ever be heard.

Q: Is there any focus on identifying protection needs?

A: The system is built to move people quickly away from the coast, not to identify those who might need protection. Speed takes priority over rights.

Q: How does the public narrative shape these policies?

A: If the story told to the public is that borders are under siege, then any amount of control seems justified...I have seen entire boat groups treated as if they were a single problem to be solved, not as human beings with different needs.

Q: Do you think the EU's technical role is being misunderstood?

A: Yes, a lot of people still think of our role as purely administrative, just providing support or logistics. But in reality, when we supply the tools and coordinate procedures, we influence the outcomes more than people realize.

Q: What happens when legal clarity is missing?

A: It causes hesitation. People on the ground might want to help or do the right thing, but they are unsure what is allowed or required. That leads to delays or inconsistent treatment, and ultimately it is the migrants who suffer from that confusion.

Q: Are there consequences to this lack of structure?

A: Absolutely. Without a clear process, you cannot ensure fair treatment. Some people are given a chance to explain their case, while others are moved on without even knowing they had a right to speak up.

Q: Is the Tunisian side prepared to handle protection screenings?

A: They are doing what they can, but the system just is not there. There is no national asylum law and no framework for assessing who might need protection. Everything depends on whether someone from UNHCR or an NGO happens to be there that day.

Q: What does that mean for people who are intercepted?

A: It means the outcome of your case can depend on luck. If you are intercepted at a moment when protection staff are present, you might get support. If not, you could be sent inland without ever speaking to someone who could help you.

Q: Is there any opportunity to appeal a return decision?

A: In most cases, no. People are transferred very quickly. There is no formal hearing, no legal advice, and no time to ask questions. By the time they understand what is happening, it is already too late.

Q: What about coordination between EU institutions and Tunisian authorities?

A: It exists, but it is very operational. The focus is on movement and logistics. Discussions tend to center on schedules, boats, and equipment, not on whether people are being informed of their rights or given legal options.

Q: Do you think the EU should be more involved in protection guarantees?

A: Yes. If we are involved in shaping how operations work, we cannot ignore the protection side. It is not enough to say that it is up to the partner country. If our systems are part of the process, then so is our responsibility.

Q: Are there particular gaps that concern you most?

A: One of the biggest ones is legal aid. People arrive after long, dangerous journeys, and there is no one there to explain what rights they have or what they can ask for. Without that basic help, due process becomes almost impossible.

Q: Do people actually ask to seek asylum when intercepted?

A: Some do, yes. But they are rarely heard. Sometimes they ask a guard, sometimes a translator, and sometimes no one really knows who is supposed to receive that request. The system is not built to capture those moments clearly.

Q: Has there been any push for improvement?

A: There are proposals. Some people within the EU and among partners have raised the need for mobile legal teams or designated protection officers at key ports. But it is slow. Change takes time, and meanwhile the situation continues.

Q: Do people understand what is happening to them?

A: Often not. Migrants are tired, scared, and many do not speak the local language. They might be moved two or three times in one day without ever being told where they are going or why. That uncertainty affects their mental health too.

Q: How do operational goals affect the way people are treated?

A: The pressure is on fast turnover. Get people off the boats, clear the area, prepare for the next group. That kind of urgency leaves very little room for legal assessments or even basic humanitarian care.

Q: What happens after people are transferred inland?

A: That is where visibility really drops. Once they are moved inland, it becomes very difficult to trace what happened to them. You cannot follow up, and they often disappear from any kind of support network.

Q: Do you believe there is political will to change this?

A: I think there is awareness, but will is another question. Migration is politically sensitive, and no one wants to appear too soft. So even small changes that would make the system fairer can be delayed or avoided entirely.

**Interview Transcript 6: JHA
Counselor, Permanent Representation
of the Netherlands to the EU**

**Interview conducted in English on 30
January 2025 in Brussels
Duration: 30 minutes**

Q: How does legal accountability factor into cooperation agreements?

A: Treaty articles provide the mandate for cooperation, but they also create an accountability hook...if those principles are ignored, the legal basis for the partnership itself can be challenged.

Q: What drives funding priorities in these partnerships?

A: Payments chase delivery of surveillance capacity; rights compliance demands a separate monitoring track, and that track is often thinner on the ground.

Q: What happens when operational efficiency outpaces legal readiness?

A: The better we get at finding the boats, the more important it becomes to have the protection process ready at the other end, otherwise we are just pushing the problem into a smaller space.

Q: In your view, what is the EU's main motivation in external cooperation on migration?

A: It is mostly about managing arrivals. That is the political driver. Everyone wants to show they are reducing numbers, and that shapes both the tone and the priorities of these agreements.

Q: How do those priorities influence what is actually implemented?

A: It means things like patrols and infrastructure upgrades get funded first. The softer side, like legal aid or training on protection standards, is often delayed or not funded at all.

Q: What role do embassies or EU representations play in operational planning?

A: We often facilitate dialogue, but the real planning happens between the Commission and the security services. Our job is more to support coordination and make sure member state interests are represented.

Q: What happens when there is tension between human rights and operational goals?

A: That tension is constant. Everyone in the room understands the human rights language, but when time is short and boats are expected, the priority shifts toward efficiency.

Q: How is success reported back to Brussels?

A: Usually through numbers. Interceptions, returns, fewer departures. Those are the metrics that show up in the reporting. Rights outcomes are much harder to quantify, and that makes them easier to overlook.

Q: Are protection needs raised in internal meetings?

A: They are mentioned, but often not with much depth. It tends to be more of a box to check than a core element of the conversation.

Q: What do you think is missing in the oversight process?

A: Independent monitoring that can actually report back publicly. Right now, most oversight is internal. That is not enough if you want real accountability.

Q: Do national parliaments have any role in reviewing these agreements?

A: In theory, yes. But the way these agreements are structured often puts them outside the usual scrutiny channels. They are framed as operational or technical rather than political.

Q: What happens when something goes wrong on the ground?

A: Usually it is handled quietly. Investigations, if they happen, are not public. And by the time any findings are made, the situation on the ground has already changed.

Q: Is there space for civil society in these partnerships?

A: That really depends on the country. In some places, civil society is part of the process. In others, it is seen as a risk or even a nuisance. It is very uneven.

Q: Do you think the EU is aware of how its policies play out locally?

A: I think the EU is aware in general terms, but the day-to-day consequences are not always visible to decision-makers. It is very different reading a report and being there in person.

Q: How should cooperation agreements evolve to be more balanced?

A: They need to build in protection requirements as part of the operational plan, not as a side note. If the whole agreement is built around returns and interceptions, everything else will fall behind.

Q: Are the legal obligations of member states diluted by joint operations?

A: That is one of the core risks. If everyone assumes someone else is responsible, then no one actually takes ownership of the legal standards that are supposed to apply.

Q: How does your office view the future of these partnerships?

A: We see more of them coming. There is political momentum for externalization. The challenge is whether they can be structured in a way that meets both operational goals and legal commitments.

Q: What would you say to someone who believes these agreements are just about stopping migration?

A: I would say they are not wrong, but they are only seeing part of the picture. The agreements also include cooperation on development, return, and even legal migration. The problem is that the balance is off right now.

**Interview Transcript 7: Legal Officer,
DG Migration and Home Affairs,
European Commission**

**Interview conducted in English on 5
June 2025 via Google Meet**

Duration: 30 minutes

Q: How would you describe the EU's goals in working with Tunisia?

A: It is not just about sending money or equipment. It is about making sure Tunisia's coast guard works in a way that matches EU priorities.

Q: How do legal commitments influence cooperation?

A: The Compact may be a soft law, but politically it sets the tone...it becomes harder to justify operational shortcuts when both sides have signed on to broad human rights language.

Q: How are program goals defined?

A: Deliverables are defined at the level of surveillance capacity and coordination functions, while rights safeguards are flagged as mandatory operating standards.

Q: What role does EU funding play over time?

A: The sequencing of these instruments was not accidental. EUTF money got the system started, and NDICI money locked it in place.

Q: What is the EU's view on Tunisia's ability to uphold protection obligations?

A: There is an ongoing concern that even though Tunisia is improving its capacity to intercept people at sea, it does not yet have the legal and institutional systems needed to properly protect them. We know people are being stopped and returned, but we cannot always confirm if those people were given a fair chance to ask for asylum or legal help. That is a serious gap.

Q: What accountability measures exist for EU-funded border operations?

A: We ask for reports and updates from the partners we fund, but most of the time the review process happens internally. Independent observers are not always involved. That makes it

hard to respond quickly if something goes wrong. In some places, there is no way to verify what happens after someone is picked up at sea.

Q: What challenges do you face in aligning priorities with partner governments?

A: The biggest challenge is that our goals do not always match up. We want to reduce dangerous crossings, but we also want people to have access to protection if they qualify. Sometimes our partners focus only on stopping departures. That leaves no room for the other part of the agreement, which is making sure people's rights are respected.

Q: How do internal EU dynamics affect external cooperation?

A: Inside the EU, there is pressure to show that external partnerships are working. People want to see numbers that say fewer people are arriving. But if that is the only thing we measure, then we ignore what happens to the people who were stopped. Some may have had real reasons to flee, and if we don't track that, we miss a big part of the picture.

Q: Are there examples where human rights concerns changed operations?

A: Yes, there have been times when we stopped certain parts of a project because of reports of abuse or poor conditions. But that is not always easy to do. Ending cooperation can mean losing whatever influence we had. Sometimes we have to stay engaged and try to improve things from inside the relationship, but even then, change can be slow.

Q: What would you change about the current system?

A: I think we need stronger conditions on our funding. Right now we mostly measure how many operations happened or how many people were intercepted. We should also be asking how many people got legal advice, how many were referred for protection, and whether anyone filed complaints. That kind of information would help us understand the full picture.

Q: How does the EU coordinate with humanitarian organisations in these settings?

A: We try to keep in touch with humanitarian groups, especially ones that are active in camps or reception centres. But in some places they are not allowed into the areas where people are taken after being intercepted. That means even we do not always know what is happening. It would help if civil society had more access and more support.

Q: Do you think the soft law nature of these agreements is a problem?

A: It depends. Soft law gives us flexibility to move quickly, but it also means there are fewer ways to hold people accountable. If something goes wrong, we cannot always go to court or rely on clear rules. That can be frustrating, especially when rights are involved.

Q: What makes it hard to talk about rights in operational meetings?

A: The teams on the ground are under pressure. They are managing boats, equipment, and logistics. It is not that they do not care about rights, but the structure of their job focuses on fast results. Unless rights are treated as part of the operation from the start, they end up being seen as someone else's responsibility.

Q: Is there political support within the Commission for stronger rights safeguards?

A: Yes, many people in the institutions want to see better rights protection. But there is always a trade-off with political reality. Migration is sensitive. Some Member States push for strong external control and fewer arrivals. That makes it harder to insist on rights protections without facing pushback.

Q: What role does transparency play in improving these partnerships?

A: Transparency is key. If people cannot see what is happening in these operations, they cannot ask the right questions. That goes for journalists, for civil society, and even for other EU institutions. More openness would actually help improve public trust and make the system more balanced.

**Interview Transcript 8: Legal
Advisor, VluchtelingenWerk
Nederland (Dutch Council for
Refugees)**

**Interview conducted in English on 6
June 2025 via Google Meet
Duration: 60 minutes**

Q: How do you see success being measured in EU partnerships?

A: If what counts as success is measured in boats stopped rather than in protection claims processed, then protection has been left out of the operational priorities.

Q: How do you think success is measured in EU migration partnerships?

A: Honestly, it often feels like success is measured by how many boats are stopped, not by how many people actually get a fair chance to ask for protection. That's worrying because it leaves the rights side of things out of the picture completely.

Q: What would a better version of success look like?

A: I think we should be asking, "Are people who need protection actually getting it?" Are they being informed about their rights? Are asylum claims being processed fairly? Those are the questions we should focus on, not just numbers or border control.

Q: What do people tell you after they've been intercepted?

A: A lot of people are just confused. They don't even know where they are or what's going to happen next. Some think they're being taken to safety, but then they end up detained or pushed back. There's rarely any explanation.

Q: What kind of support do people need at that point?

A: The first thing they need is information. Clear, simple information in a language they understand. Just knowing what's happening, what their options are...that can make a huge difference. But often, that never happens.

Q: Are legal protections strong enough on paper?

A: The laws are usually there, but they're not followed. It's one thing to have rights written

down in an agreement. It's another thing entirely to make sure people actually experience those rights in real life.

Q: What role can organisations like yours play?

A: We can help make sure people are seen and heard. But for that to happen, we need access. We need authorities to let us in and take what we say seriously. Right now, too often we're kept on the sidelines.

Q: Is it hard to follow up on individual cases?

A: Very hard. People are moved around with no warning, sometimes without any record. By the time we find out they need help, they might already be gone. It's incredibly frustrating because you want to help, but the system is working against you.

Q: Is there any real oversight after someone is intercepted?

A: Honestly, not much. Some areas are totally closed off to NGOs and lawyers. We rely on secondhand info, and that's not good enough. There needs to be real, independent oversight if we're going to hold anyone accountable.

Q: What worries you most about these EU deals?

A: It's that they let the EU shift responsibility while still being involved. Just because someone is intercepted by a partner country doesn't mean the EU can wash its hands of the outcome...especially if it's EU money, equipment, or training making it happen.

Q: If you could redesign the cooperation model, what would you do differently?

A: I'd start by making protection the main goal, not just control. And I'd tie funding to actual rights outcomes, not just to stopping migration. Also, open things up...make the system more transparent and let independent monitors in.

Q: Are there cases that really stuck with you?

A: Yes. I remember a young woman who had been intercepted twice. She said no one ever asked why she was trying to leave or gave her a chance to explain. She just got pushed back, again and again. That kind of story stays with you.

Q: How well is international law being respected in these partnerships?

A: In theory, it's supposed to guide everything. But in practice, it often gets sidelined. People

talk about legal commitments after problems show up...not before. It should be the foundation, not the backup.

Q: Do you think the general public really understands how these policies play out?

A: Not really. People mostly hear about numbers or political headlines. They don't hear about the real human experiences...the exhaustion, the fear, the confusion. That needs to change.

Q: Have you seen any progress in specific areas?

A: A few projects have made things better, especially where there's good cooperation and funding used wisely. But those are the exception, not the rule. Most of the time, there's still a long way to go.

Q: How does all this affect migrants' trust in the system?

A: It damages it completely. If you're told you have rights, but no one helps you use them, why would you trust the system? And once that trust is gone, it's really hard to rebuild.

Q: What's one thing you'd say to policymakers working on new deals?

A: Talk to the people on the ground. Listen to migrants, NGOs, lawyers...people who actually see what's happening. If you only focus on reducing migration numbers, you're going to miss the point of protection entirely.

**Interview Transcript 9: Protection
Associate, UNHCR Tunisia Country
Office**

**Interview conducted in English on 7
June 2025 via Google Meet
Duration: 60 minutes**

Q: How soon are you able to engage with people after interception?

A: Sometimes our first contact with an intercepted group is when they are already being prepared for return, and at that stage, legal intervention is almost impossible.

Q: Is there any guarantee that people are interviewed after being returned?

A: The sea patrols have become faster, more coordinated, but there is no guarantee that those intercepted will ever see a proper asylum interview. They are sent back to shore, and the process stops there.

Q: What happens if someone is not registered right away?

A: If someone is not registered at the point of arrival, it becomes almost impossible to trace them later for an asylum interview.

Q: What are the common obstacles to registration and support?

A: People often disappear from the system before we can register them; by the time we are informed, they may already be in the south with no legal assistance.

Q: How are people treated upon arrival?

A: People arrive at the port visibly exhausted, sometimes ill, and there is no structured moment where they are told they can apply for asylum. The priority seems to be to move them along quickly, not to give them the time or space to speak.

Q: Do people know they can challenge return decisions?

A: Intercepted people often have no idea that they can challenge a return, and they are never brought before any legal authority where such a challenge could even be made.

Q: How does mistrust develop after failed asylum attempts?

A: You meet people who have tried to claim asylum once, were turned away without explanation, and now refuse to go near any authority.

Q: What are people's expectations versus their experience?

A: People arrive onshore believing they will be able to explain why they fled, but the reality is that nobody is listening. They are tired, frightened, and often do not even know where they are being taken.

Q: How does stigma affect daily life after interception?

A: When the state talks about you as a threat, even if you are just a person looking for safety, it changes how everyone else sees you. Landlords do not want to rent to you, employers avoid you, and the police feel justified in pushing you out. It is not only about the law...it is about the whole atmosphere.

Q: What happens inside detention facilities?

A: You have to understand that once someone is in those facilities, they disappear from view. Even their friends and family do not know where they are. They can be moved at night, and no one is told. It is like they stop existing in the eyes of the outside world.